

List of abbreviations used in this document: **AERA:** Adaptive Emission Reduction Approach; **AIS:** Antarctic Ice Sheet; **AMOC:** Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation; **CMIP:** Coupled Model Intercomparison Project; **COP:** Conference of the Parties (United Nations Climate Change); **DEC:** Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication; **DMP:** Data Management Plan; **EC:** European Commission; **ECCA:** European Climate Change Adaptation Conference; **ENSO:** El Niño–Southern Oscillation; **EO:** Expected outcome; **ESGF:** Earth System Grid Federation; **ESM:** Earth System Model; **EU:** European Union; **EWI:** Early Warning Indicator; **GIS:** Greenland Ice Sheet; **GWL:** Global Warming Level; **HPC:** High Performance Computing; **IPBES:** Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services; **IPCC:** The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change; **IPCC AR:** The IPCC climate change Assessment Report; **ISIMIP:** Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project <https://www.isimip.org/>; **OBGC:** Ocean Biogeochemistry; **OptimESM:** EU-Horizon project developing of high resolution ESMs; **SPG:** Subpolar Gyre; **SROCC:** Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a changing Climate; **SST:** Sea Surface Temperature; **TE:** Tipping Event; **TIPMIP:** Tipping Element Model Intercomparison Project <https://tipmip.pik-potsdam.de/>; **TP:** Tipping Point; **TRL:** Technology Readiness Level; **WAIS:** West Antarctic Ice Sheet; **WCRP:** World Climate Research Programme.

1. Excellence

1.1 Objectives and ambition

1.1.1 Objectives

Anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases and land-use change are warming the planet, with global surface temperatures now around 1.1°C above pre-industrial values (IPCC AR6). Despite efforts to reduce emissions, global warming continues unabated, with increasing likelihood the warming targets of the Paris Agreement will be temporarily or permanently exceeded. Several Earth system phenomena are increasingly at risk of rapid, potentially irreversible change (Lenton et al. 2008, 2019), with some tipping points (e.g., West Antarctic (WAIS) and Greenland Ice Sheets (GIS), low-latitude coral reefs and permafrost thaw) at risk even at modest levels of warming (IPCC SR1.5, IPCC SROCC, IPCC AR6). Tipping of Earth system elements may result in severe, even catastrophic, consequences for ecosystems, biodiversity and society.

Paleo-records provide evidence for sudden shifts in the stability of ice sheets, vegetation and ocean circulation on timescales short enough (decades to centuries) to challenge the capacity of human societies to adapt (Brovkin et al. 2021). The abrupt Dansgaard–Oeschger warming events seen in the Greenland ice core, which occurred multiple times during the last glacial cycle, correspond to temperature increases in excess of 15 °C in Greenland and several degrees in Europe over a few decades, causing major impacts to hydroclimate and carbon cycling, with evidence for crossing of thresholds in regional marine and terrestrial ecosystems.

Evidence exists that tipping points (TPs) may be interconnected across different components and regions of the Earth system and exceeding a TP in one system may increase the risk of abrupt changes in other systems (Rocha et al. 2018). For example, Greenland ice melt may destabilise the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) in a warming climate (Swingedouw et al. 2007, Wunderling et al. 2021) and has also been shown to interact with the WAIS (Swingedouw et al. 2009, Sinet et al. 2023). An abrupt decline in AMOC could have far reaching impacts on: the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), mid-latitude storm tracks, the Amazon forest and Sahel vegetation (Defrance et al. 2017), as well as terrestrial (Bellomo et al. 2021), and marine carbon uptake (Perez et al. 2013), with consequent effects on ocean biogeochemistry (OBGC) and marine ecosystems (Osman et al. 2019). Rapid loss of Arctic sea ice will also affect OBGC, leading to an increase oceanic carbon uptake and acidification (Richaud et al. 2022). While interaction between tipping elements may induce a cascade of tipping, the dynamical coupling of these elements may also result in the opposite effect of stabilising the system. Using a conceptual model of the AMOC, GIS and WAIS, Sinet et al (2023) show that collapse of the WAIS may stabilise the AMOC, thereby preventing a global cascading event. There is thus large uncertainty in both the triggering and impacts of a tipping, and progress is needed to understand and simulate these phenomena in fully coupled Earth system models.

Dynamical theory has shown that a number of systems become more sensitive to small perturbations before tipping, often manifested as a slower recovery from perturbations, which can potentially serve as an early warning indicator (EWI, Boers et al. 2021). However, tipping signals in paleo-records and observations are sparse and the reliability of such EWIs is debated. The use of remotely sensed data for EWI detection is promising but remains challenging (Swingedouw et al. 2019).

Another poorly understood topic concerns the link between rare climate extremes and TPs. Paleo-data indicate past abrupt changes in ocean circulation may have been triggered by extreme freshwater release into the ocean (Gottschalk et al. 2015), and the Great Salinity Anomalies in the 1960s caused a substantial reduction in ocean convection in the Labrador Sea (Mikolajewicz et al. 2005). Marine heatwaves have been identified as the main driver for regime shifts in ecosystem composition (Wernberg et al. 2016, Smith et al. 2023) and extreme atmospheric poleward heat transport can trigger rapid loss of sea ice and land ice melting (Wille et al 2022).

While climate change is not yet one of the top drivers of biodiversity loss (Jaureguiberry et al., 2022), it is emerging to impact biodiversity across scales, including decline in body condition (Bush et al. 2020), changes in phenology (Kubelka et al. 2022), shift of species to higher altitudes (Kubelka et al. 2022) or towards the poles (Soultan et al. 2022). Ongoing climate change, including tipping events (TEs) of key phenomena may further increase pressure on biodiversity (Ureta et al. 2022), although evidence remains sparse. Persistence of extreme temperature or precipitation impacts the ecology and habitat size of different disease vectors; vector population growth rates and dynamics, distribution, seasonality and transmission patterns (Liu-Helmersson et al. 2014). A slowdown of the AMOC may result in a southward shift of the ITCZ leading to decreased rainfall over the Sahel, with potential impacts on malaria transmission (Chemison et al. 2021).

Most frequently cited tipping elements, such as ice sheet loss, permafrost thaw, AMOC collapse, Amazon dieback, and ecosystem shifts involve complex interactions between physical and biogeochemical systems, with competing feedbacks in response to climate change, and deep uncertainty along the entire chain. Earth system models (ESMs) are increasing in their process realism and now include key interactive components such as ice sheets, dynamic vegetation and wildfires, human land-use, permafrost and full cycles of important greenhouse-gases and nutrients. Thanks to recent technology development such fully coupled ESMs are able to be applied for long climate change simulations at resolution of $\sim 1^\circ$ (~ 100 km) today, and will be even run at increased resolution of $0.25^\circ - 0.5^\circ$ ($\sim 30-50$ km) over the coming few years. ESMs therefore represent a powerful tool for investigating TPs and their interactions, feedbacks and impacts across the Earth system.

Current understanding of TPs is based primarily on conceptual models (e.g. Wunderling et al. 2021, Sinet et al. 2023), models of a single Earth system component (e.g. ice sheet models), Earth system models of intermediate complexity, or physical climate models (e.g., the North Atlantic Hosing Model Intercomparison Project, Jackson et al. 2022). Such models do not fully represent the range of processes, interactions and feedbacks across the full Earth system, particularly interactions between physical and biogeochemical components. ESMs offer an important, more complete, extension to the present portfolio of tools to investigate TPs in the Earth system.

Using knowledge gained from latest ESM models and observational constraints, **the primary objective of TipESM is to deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.**

TipESM will achieve its overarching objective through several specific objectives linked to the project work plan and its outcomes (Table 1.1).

Table 1.1: the specific objectives (SO) of TipESM are directly linked to dedicated work packages (the main WP targeting each SO is in bold). Each SO is measurable and verifiable by Key performance indicators (KPIs)

SO	Specific objectives and KPIs	WP(s)
SO1	To design and perform a set of coordinated experiments with coupled ESMs to support the investigation of Earth system TPs at different levels of global warming. KPIs: ESM experiment protocol for the international ESM community. Realisation of these simulations with the six project ESMs, and dissemination of the data via ESGF data nodes (Deliverables: D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3. Milestoens: MS1, MS2, MS3, MS4)	1,2,4,5

SO2	To identify climate TPs in the CMIP6 archive and dedicated runs from TipESM (SO1) and previous EU projects, and improve our understanding of the processes underpinning such TPs and their impacts across the Earth system. KPIs: A new catalogue of the likelihood of crossing TPs as a function of global warming, combined with an assessment of the driving processes and the impact of each tipping event on the Earth system . (Deliverables: D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3).	1,2
SO3	To investigate the robustness and potential (ir)reversibility of climate TPs; KPIs: A synthesis report on the (ir)reversibility and robustness of key TPs and the dependency on the rate, magnitude and duration of global warming levels (GWLs). (Deliverables: D3.1 and D3.2).	1,3
SO4	To identify precursors of climate and ecological TPs, and develop reliable early warning indicators based on ESM models and observations. KPIs: A register of TP EWIs; recommendations for future observational systems. (Deliverables: D4.1 and D4.2).	1,4,5, 6
SO5	To identify the risk of a cascade from one climate tipping event to others. KPI: A report on interactions between tipping events, across the Earth system; assessment of the likelihood of TP cascades. (Deliverables D5.1 and D5.2).	1,5, 6, 7
SO6	To identify tipping events in ecological and societal systems, with a focus on the climate-drivers of these events, emphasising biodiversity, human health and habitability. KPIs: A report detailing ecological and societal TPs and climate thresholds that may cause tipping. (Deliverables: D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3. Milestones: MS6 and MS7).	1,3,6
SO7	To provide new understanding on the climate, societal and ecosystem consequences of crossing climate thresholds and TPs. KPIs: A report on the impact of climate tipping events on natural and human systems, encompassing the vulnerability and exposure of these systems. (Deliverables: D7.1, D7.2, D7.3 Milestones: MS5, MS8).	1,7, 8
SO8	To deliver a risk register of future TPs and a set of safe emission pathways to minimise the chance of crossing such TPs through engagement with stakeholders and by feeding tailored information to adaptation strategies via ClimateAdapt and European Environmental Agency, European Climate and Health Observatory, ECDC, UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDDR), UNEP. KPIs: A risk register of the likelihood of crossing climate TPs and their consequences for climate, ecosystems and society; safe future emissions pathways sampled by the project ESMs. (D8.1, D8.2, D8.3. Milestones: MS9, MS10)	1-7,8, 9,10
SO9	To provide policy guidance to the EC, IPCC, IPBES and the UNFCC Global Stocktake, on the likelihood and consequences of crossing climate TPs and mitigation options to minimise the chance of such events. KPIs: A summary of the main project findings for non-specialists and leaflets highlighting potential impacts on a) human systems and society b) ecosystems and biodiversity. (Deliverables: D9.2, D9.4, D9.5, D9.7, D10.1 and D10.2)	1-8, 9,10

TipESM directly addresses the call [HORIZON-CL5-2023-D1-01-02] “Climate related tipping points” and contributes to all expected outcomes (EOs). TipESM will apply a set of the newest ESMs, including recent improvements to a number of key processes in ice sheets, vegetation and land use, permafrost and biogeochemical cycles. TipESM will organise an international collaboration to develop a protocol and a common set of ESM experiments following the protocol to analyse the occurrence of tipping elements at different levels of future warming and warming overshoots (SO1). This will be based on simulations started in the EU-Horizon project OptimESM, and will closely collaborate with the WCRP projects CMIP (Coupled Model Intercomparison project) and TIPMIP (Box 2). These ensemble ESM experiments will be available for international communities of climate modelling and impact modelling to facilitate research of potential effects of TPs on climate, ecosystems and society. Based on these simulations, TipESM will investigate TPs, their driving processes, early warning signals and cascading effects within

the climate system and on eco- and societal systems (SO2, SO3, SO4, SO5). Including the most important components of the Earth system in our ESMs enables TipESM to identify potentially unknown tipping elements and investigate their precursors and consequences (SO2, SO4). TipESM brings together expertise from natural science, ecology and social science to investigate both the role of incremental climate change on TPs in ecosystems and social systems, and the impact of crossing climate TPs for society, ecosystems and biodiversity (SO6, SO7). The TipESM risk register will provide input to adaptation strategies (SO8, SO9). Finally, TipESM will advance the novel adaptive emission reduction approach (AERA) in ESMs to include tipping elements to deliver safe mitigation pathways that minimise the risk of crossing the most dangerous TPs and extreme and compound event thresholds (SO8, SO9).

1.1.2 Ambition

The IPCC AR6 report (IPCC 2023) highlighted that limiting global warming to well below 2°C is becoming extremely challenging. Recent research suggest TPs in the Earth system, with potentially devastating impacts on ecosystems and society, may be reached earlier than previously thought (McKay et al. 2022). Societies and policymakers require more robust knowledge on these TPs and their potential impacts. TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to deliver new insight to six key TP challenges.

a. Simulating TPs in the Earth system with the latest generation of ESMs

TipESM will use the most advanced ESMs, which extend physical climate models (GCMs), through inclusion of important elements at risk from global warming, such as continental ice sheets, marine ecosystems, permafrost, vegetation dynamics and wildfires, and the full carbon cycle, all elements being fully coupled. TipESM will develop an ESM protocol with WCRP TIPMIP, and realise these experiments with six project's ESMs. The protocol will include CO₂-emission driven ramp-up runs, zero-emission stabilisation runs at various GWLs, and ramp-down simulations back to a 1.5°C and pre-industrial levels. These simulations will provide a unique database to examine the risk and robustness of various TPs, their precursors, (ir)reversibility, and the effect of overshooting warming targets on this risk. In addition, the ESMs will be used to perform specific experiments to study in detail the potential for a cascading impact of one TP on other parts of the Earth system and the potential impacts of climate TEs on human and ecological systems.

b. New knowledge on climate TPs and their driving processes

Knowledge on climate TPs and their downstream effects is still hampered by an incomplete process understanding and poor model representation of important feedbacks. We capitalise on recent ESM improvements (in e.g. CRESCENDO, ESM2025) targeted at including various feedbacks hitherto neglected in physical climate models and simpler models. With improved data-search algorithms, ESM archives (e.g. CMIP6 and OptimESM) will be scanned to update previous and ongoing efforts to document TPs and abrupt changes in the Earth system, now explicitly including biogeochemical cycles in the land and ocean (extending efforts in COMFORT), and produce a catalogue of these events in the TipESM simulations. In addition, we will isolate the feedbacks and chains of processes leading to TEs, including analysis of the new set of TipESM warming overshoot runs.

The simulated abrupt changes and tipping signals will be evaluated against observations and relevant paleo-data. Downstream effects on atmospheric circulation (i.e., jet streams and regional modes) and weather extremes will be assessed. In addition, we will investigate climate thresholds that lead to tipping in ecosystems and society, developing a new risk-landscape for such TEs. This will result in unique information on the risk of exceeding TPs in various warming scenarios at different GWLs, as well as guidance for pathways to minimise the risk of crossing TPs.

c. Early warning indicators and the risk for cascades of TPs in the climate and ecosystems

An important question for climate adaptation is whether early warning of abrupt changes and TPs can be provided sufficiently in advance. TipESM will develop new early warning methods, using space-for-time substitution (e.g. Dakos et al. 2010) applied to new systems, to gain insight from remote sensing data. We will go beyond common EWIs, based on identifying changes (slowing down) of resilience in time-series. EWIs will first be tested in observations and paleo-data, and the robustness and failure risk of specific EWIs will then be tested in models.

TipESM will improve our understanding of potential remote interactions in time and space between Earth system TPs. We will build on our core set of ESM simulations (*TipESM_core*, see Table 1.2b) and perform experiments where we deliberately trigger a major TE (i.e., AMOC; WAIS; Amazon dieback) to investigate the effects of one TP on other potential TPs. We will extend existing knowledge on TP cascades by (a) focusing on cascades not investigated before and (b) accounting for feedbacks across Earth system components.

The risk that extreme climate events trigger TPs is also poorly understood. Paleo-data and observations suggest certain events, such as extreme atmospheric and marine heatwaves or Arctic freshwater releases, may affect processes linked to tipping occurrence, but it remains unclear if such extremes can cause actual tipping. TipESM will advance

knowledge on this topic by a) scanning existing and TipESM simulations for extreme events occurring in advance of TEs, and b) investigating if specific extremes trigger TEs at different GWLs.

d. Identifying climate change-driven TPs in ecosystem and society

Despite the potentially devastating impact of climate tipping on ecosystems and society, incremental climate change may also lead to thresholds being exceeded (e.g. temperature or sea level thresholds) that lead to TEs in ecosystems and society, such as biodiversity loss or a permanent displacement of people. TipESM will advance knowledge on a range of systems at risk of tipping and identify the climate thresholds and drivers that may lead to tipping.

We will analyse three terrestrial ecosystems: forest and savanna biomes in Sub-Saharan Africa, the Amazon rainforest, and mountain ecosystems. Further, we will identify thresholds for marine species and the conditions under which certain habitats would be lost. We focus on ocean regions most vulnerable to deoxygenation and acidification, such as the tropical Pacific, Arctic, upwelling regions and deep-sea habitats. We will develop conceptual models for a fjord system in Greenland and identify thresholds at which gradual changes in ocean stratification and the climate-driven retreat of marine terminating glaciers lead to tipping in fish species.

TipESM will go beyond the state-of-the-art, by analysing social TPs caused by climate-driven changes in extreme events: (1) permanent human displacement caused by the frequency of disasters being shorter than the reconstruction time; (2) consequences for households not able to recover between tropical cyclones that may become trapped in poverty.

e. New knowledge on the impacts of climate-tipping events on ecosystems and society

We will develop and apply impact models to analyse multi-sectoral impacts related to climate TEs, and analyse consequences for the UN Sustainable Development Goals. TipESM will deliver new knowledge in several areas. We will investigate the impact of ice sheet collapse on sea level and consequently, storm surges and coastal flooding. We will assess how rapid increases in temperature and humidity, associated with climate tipping, coupled with changed seasonal timings, leads to heat stress, wildfires, drought and water shortage. A special focus will be on moist heat waves and temperature-humidity-mortality relationships, including human and livestock physiological limits and crop failure, to assess impacts on human habitability and migration. We will provide recommendations for acceptable heat stress limits in the context of “climate refugee” status due to climate-induced inhabitability.

Climate TPs altering the Sahel/West African monsoon may have a dramatic effect on malaria incidence and propagation across Africa, as well as on the altitude colonisation in the highlands of Africa, South America and the Indian subcontinent. Similarly, multiple Arctic ice TEs (e.g. GIS, Barents Sea, Arctic winter sea ice) may have a significant impact on the hydrological cycle and diarrhoeal disease outbreaks and distribution (Parkinson & Evengård, 2009). TipESM will quantify the effect of such tipping on the distribution of infectious diseases and their vectors, with a focus on malaria, diarrhoeal diseases and zoonotic spillover. Potential parameter spaces for ecosystem collapse and spillover will be evaluated under different ESM scenarios.

f. Future TP risks and safe mitigation emission pathways

TipESM will provide a unique TP risk register following the IPCC Venn diagram. This will synthesise knowledge on the likelihood and impacts of crossing TPs. It will include information on tipping element thresholds, timescales and impacts at global and regional scales such as loss of habitat, economic and human health risks. To reduce uncertainty, we will constrain the ESM and impact projections using observation-based constraints of key physical and biogeochemical processes. For this purpose, we will use artificial intelligence (AI) methods integrated in an emergent constraint toolbox dedicated to reducing uncertainty in likelihood estimates of TP crossing.

TipESM will develop safe emission pathways to avoid crossing TPs and extreme event thresholds. We will advance the Adaptive Emission Reduction Approach (AERA, Terhaar et al. 2022) including multiple targets beyond global warming to avoid the impacts from potential future TEs. We will test these pathways by running the project ESMs with updated AERA code.

1.1.3 Positioning of the project

The TipESM ESMs are global climate models with fully integrated and interactive Earth system components including: the carbon cycle, marine and terrestrial biogeochemical cycles, dynamical vegetation, atmospheric chemistry, continental ice sheets and, in some cases, interactive wildfires, permafrost and closed cycles of methane. These models are currently under evaluation (e.g. in OptimESM), and thus ready for use at the beginning of TipESM (TRL8). Modification of the ESMs may be needed (TRL9), for example to support the *TipESM_forced* experiments (see table 1.2b) where we deliberately induce TEs in the models.

The original AERA code was designed in the H2020 project 4C (Terhaar et al. 2022) and focuses solely on global warming as a target. In TipESM, we will extend AERA to include selected tipping elements (e.g., AMOC, Amazon dieback, Arctic and Southern Ocean acidification, *etc.*) as additional targets. The modified AERA code will be tested with two simple models, the Bern3D-LPX and FaIR, before being run with the TipESM ESMs to quantify safe mitigation pathways.

The TP search and detection algorithms are fully mature and essentially those used in Drijfhout et al, (2015). We will add (and develop) a new version of the algorithm to detect rare extreme events based on extreme-value theory and return time assessment. Thus, at the start of the project this part of the algorithm is in a TRL2 phase, but will mature during the project to TRL9. In addition, we will use and develop a Machine Learning algorithm, presently in an intermediate state of maturity (tested on one model and variable), alongside our mature algorithms. If successful, with improved search and detection, this prototype will be developed to full maturity

Impact models from ISIMIP (The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project) are well-developed, with an established protocol (TRL8), and are part of the 3rd ISIMIP round (ISIMIP3). These models have been evaluated extensively, with the latest ISIMIP3 evaluation complete before the start of TipESM. Our first major advance will be integration of the impact models with observed biodiversity and household survey data to demonstrate their applicability for assessing ecological and social tipping (initially TRL2, becoming TRL4). Our second major advance will be evaluation of the identified ecological and social TPs, which will further integrate Earth system and impact modelling.

Emergent constraint approaches have been in development for almost two decades (Murphy et al. 2004, Eyring et al. 2019) and are integrated in the latest IPCC assessments. Nevertheless, they remain relatively empirical, in particular with respect to the choice of predictor (the observable variable used to reduce uncertainty in projections of the same, or another variable; Ribes et al. 2021). Up to now emergent constraints have used only a limited number of predictors (e.g., Hall et al. 2019), AI offers the possibility to develop more objective techniques to identify predictors. This will allow a wider and more objective use of observations (including novel emerging observations) to constrain ESM projections. The application of emergent constraints to tipping elements has rarely been undertaken (e.g. Sgubin et al. 2017). We will develop a dedicated toolbox for this application, allowing easy sharing of results and methods.

1.2 Methodology

1.2.1 Concept

TipESM will use six world-leading ESMs (Table 1.2a), that explicitly simulate many of the key processes and process-interactions thought to likely cause tipping of physical, biogeochemical or biological systems. We will deliver a step change in our understanding of the potential triggers, and resulting consequences, of the most commonly discussed TPs (e.g. ice sheet loss, AMOC and subpolar gyre (SPG) convection, tropical forest dieback, permafrost thaw, marine deoxygenation, *etc.*), as well as investigate potentially unknown tipping elements. Combining knowledge gained from the ESMs with observations, dynamical theory and (societal and ecological) impact models, TipESM will assess the risk of exceeding key climate TPs, the consequences of a TE on other parts of the Earth system and the impact on ecology and society.

TipESM builds on the solid foundations of recent years in ESM modelling (e.g. EU-projects EMBRACE, CRESCENDO, 4C, ESM2025, OptimESM, Blue-Action) and the study of TPs (e.g. COMFORT, TiPES, TipACCs, PROTECT, EPOC and Earth Resilience in the Anthropocene), and will cluster with ongoing and new activities (e.g. other EU-projects, WCRP/FutureEarth TIPMIP and the WCRP Safe Landing Climates Lighthouse).

The conceptual framing of the project is illustrated in Fig. 1. TipESM will provide a multi-model, multi-member ensemble of ESM global warming overshoot, stabilisation and return simulations (referred to as *TipESM_core*, see Table 1.2b and Fig. 3) and perform specific ESM experiments to further support analysis in the project (referred to as *TipESM_ensemble*, *TipESM_domain* and *TipESM_force*; see Table 1.2b for an explanation of each experiment set). The ESM simulations will be analysed, together with existing simulations (e.g. CMIP6) and observations to (i) enhance our understanding of the risk of occurrence, (ir)reversibility, and processes leading to climate TEs, (ii) develop reliable EWs for a range of TPs, and (iii) investigate the potential cascade of TPs across the Earth system, including the risks of extreme climate events triggering TPs; (iv) improve our knowledge of the consequences of crossing various TPs for ecosystems and society, and knowledge of how incremental climate change may cause tipping of ecological or societal systems; (v) increase our ability to identify the likelihood of future TPs and develop emission pathways that minimise the chance of crossing such TPs. Findings from across the project will be synthesised into a *tipping points risk register* and regularly communicated to a broad range of scientific communities, policymakers and the public.

Table 1.2a List of the ESMs participating in the coordinated and targeted experiments in WP1 of TipESM

Models	Ocean model/ ocean res.	Atm. model/ atm. res.	Dyna mic vegeta tion	Carbon cycle	Ice sheet	New processes beyond CMIP6*
EC-Earth Döscher et al. (2022)	NEMO 1°	IFS ~80 km	x	x	x	Improved representation of wildfires, forestry, wetlands, permafrost, soil; Greenland ice sheet, emulator of Antarctic ice sheet response
UKESM Sellar et al. (2019)	NEMO 1°	Unified Model 1.875° x 1.25°	x	x	x	Interactive CH ₄ cycle, improved treatment of SO ₂ deposition and historical surface temperature, interactively coupled Antarctic and Greenland ice sheets.
IPSL-ESM Boucher et al. (2020)	NEMO 1°	LMDZ 2.5° x 1.25°	x	x		Upgraded with fully interactive CO ₂ , land permafrost (soil discretised), dynamical vegetation
NorESM2 Seland et al. (2020)	BLOM 1°	CAM6-N 2.5° x 2°	x	x		CMIP6 version
GFDL-ESM Dunne et al. (2020)	MOM6 0.5°	AM4.1 1°	x	x		CMIP6 version
MF-CNRM-Cerfacs Séférian et al. (2019)	NEMO 1°	ARPEGE 1.4° x 1.4°	x	x		Upgraded aerosols scheme (nitrate, etc.), Upgraded land-surface scheme (with soil discretised, crop harvest module and fire module revised, and C-permafrost

* Listed as their current status. Many ESM groups may use their new generation model version for CMIP7 if it is ready when the TipESM simulations start.

Figure 1: Conceptual diagram of TipESM showing (i) the planned science work (blocks with light blue and grey background), (ii) dissemination and exploitation plans (violet bar), in parallel with (iii) project and data management (blue bar at the bottom). The project will also (iv) use observations and existing CMIP archives (orange block) to benchmark the TipESM simulations and develop methods for identifying TPs and early warning indicators. The symbols on the right illustrate the lasting impacts the project will have (see §2).

Our approach is a well-integrated, interlinked effort split between ten work packages (WPs) as a 4-year project period. The project workflow is shown in Fig. 2, which outlines the key components of the project and their interdependencies. Many WPs share participants and build on each other. To maximise the impact of the project, dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) will occur throughout the project together with project coordination (WPs 9, 10). The description of the WPs and detailed planning is provided in §3. Below, the methodologies of the fundamental science are described (DEC activities are mostly described in §2).

Figure 2: TipESM workflow.

1.2.2 Approach

a. Simulating TPs in the Earth system with an ensemble of ESMs and dedicated experiments (WP1)

We will use six state-of-the-art ESMs and a common experiment protocol (*TipESM_core*) that samples a ramp-up (warming) phase, a zero anthropogenic CO₂ emission (stabilisation) phase and a ramp-down (cooling) phase. The ESMs will run in CO₂-emission mode, allowing interactions between the climate system and the carbon cycle, with the amount of positive (negative) emissions designed to produce a common global warming (cooling) rate across the ESMs. The protocol will be based on the idealised ESM simulations (Fig. 3) initially performed in OptimESM by a subset of the TipESM models (Box 1). Additional simulations will be developed (*e.g. sampling alternative CO₂ emission ramp-up and ramp-down rates, different GWLs and different lengths of warming overshoot before ramp-down starts*), delivering an important extension to the OptimESM runs. We will ensure the proposed experiment protocol is discussed with, and informed by, ESM groups across the world and the WCRP/FutureEarth project TIPMIP (see Box 2), resulting in an agreed coupled ESM experiment protocol for TIPMIP. An important outcome will therefore be ESM groups across the world running an identical set of overshoot and stabilisation experiments, with a common set of diagnostics saved to the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) following CMIP6/7 standards. This data will be a major resource for the international research community to increase understanding of the processes underpinning the likelihood and occurrence of TEs, including their sensitivity to global warming. The data will also be invaluable for assessing the impact of such TEs across the Earth system, on regional ecosystems and society. Finally, a coordinated protocol, focused on warming overshoot and stabilisation, will help target ESM development onto processes key to the occurrence or not of Earth system TEs.

Box 1: OptimESM Idealised Overshoot Experiments

TipESM will build on the idealised global warming overshoot experiment protocol developed in OptimESM, where four of the TipESM models will run a set of multi-century experiments in CO₂-emission mode.

These experiments are designed so that each ESM follows a similar global mean warming, stabilisation and ramp-down (cooling) pathway. Simulations branch from a pre-industrial control run and follow a constant anthropogenic CO₂ emission ramp-up, approximating a warming rate of 0.2 K/decade comparable with recent historical rates. The required CO₂ emissions are model-specific and derived from each model's value of the Transient Climate Response to cumulative carbon Emissions (TCRE). From the ramp-up simulations, zero anthropogenic emission runs will be branched at global warming levels 2°C and 3°C above pre-industrial to approximate climate stabilisation and run for 200 years. The scenarios then follow a ramp-down (cooling) pathway by inverting the CO₂ emission rate from the ramp-up phase (*i.e.* negative emission of CO₂).

In addition to the *TipESM_core* warming overshoot experiments described above, we will also run the ESMs for a number of targeted experiments (Table 1.2b). These will be designed to enable an assessment of the robustness of any identified TEs and the processes underpinning them. They will also generate an ensemble (of sufficient size and simulation length across the TE in question) to assess the impact of each event on (i) other components and regions of the Earth system and (ii) regional ecosystems and society. To achieve this, for a given model, once a TE has been identified, we will perturb the model state a suitable time in advance of the TE and rerun the simulation across the period of the original tipping. A number of such perturbations will be applied to generate an ensemble of TEs (*TipESM_ensemble*). We will investigate the robustness of each TE by modifying the perturbation size and by varying the time in advance of the event a perturbation is introduced. Analysis of these runs, combined with the more traditional multi-ESM analysis, will help establish the robustness of the TEs, the processes underpinning them, and a likelihood of occurrence for each event, and the impact on ecosystems and society.

We will also design experiments to assess the consistency of tipping occurrences to different model representations of key driving processes. For a given ESM tipping, we will identify in which model component the tipping first occurs (*e.g.* land, ocean, cryosphere) and then rerun across the event with the particular model domain in offline mode, forced by climate data from the coupled ESM over the period of investigation. If the TE also occurs in the offline simulation, we will modify key parameterisations and in that model and assess if the TE is sensitive to details of these schemes. Taking this a step further, for the example of an Amazon forest TE in ESM_A, if we can successfully recreate the same TE in the offline land model of ESM_A, driven by forcing from that model, then we

will apply the same forcing to other land vegetation models from the project ESMs and investigate whether this forcing leads to a similar behaviour (tipping or increased proximity to a TE). Similar experiments can be designed for Antarctic ice sheet tipping and SPG or AMOC collapse, using offline (regional) ice sheet or ocean models (*TipESM_domain*). These experiments will help us understand if a given TE depends on the coupling in ESM_A versus it occurring uncoupled with prescribed forcing. The experiments will also provide insight into the sensitivity of a TE, and the processes causing it and to the details of different domain-specific models. Identifying processes that are consistently important for triggering TEs, will provide guidance both for the design of early warning systems and for efforts to protect the real-world against TEs. If we can confidently identify processes that underpin TEs in our ESMs, this will help focus model development.

Figure 3: A flexible framework for modelling global warming overshoots that can sample: the rate and magnitude of global warming, the length of time above a warming level, and the rate of recovery back to a target “safe” warming level. Three examples of global mean temperature are shown. The final experiment protocol will be developed through discussion with TIPMIP and international ESM groups.

In a final set of experiments, we aim to deliberately induce tipping of key, at risk phenomena in our ESMs (*TipESM_forced*). We will cause a TE at a known level of global warming and combine this with a parallel simulation of the same ESM, at the same warming level but without the TE. The tipping and (counterfactual) non-tipping experiments will be used to assess the impact of the TE on the rest of the coupled Earth system, as well as on ecosystems and society, with the confounding role of incremental warming and climate change accounted for. Depending on findings from the *TipESM_core* experiments, we will induce a tipping (and non-tipping counterfactual) in at least one project ESM, for each of: (i) the Amazon rainforest, (ii) the West Antarctic Ice Sheet (WAIS) and (iii) the North Atlantic ocean circulation (either SPG convection or the AMOC). TEs will be induced either by changing the external forcing of the region/phenomenon in question (e.g. ocean heat flux below marine protruding ice sheets, freshwater/salinity input to regions of the North Atlantic) or by modifying key parameters in model parameterisations (e.g. sensitivity of vegetation mortality to climate drivers, ice melt sensitivity to ocean temperature, etc.). For the non-tipping simulations, we should be able to use the original ESM run, without the forcing intervention. If necessary, we will test reversing the forcing/parameter modification that caused the TE to see if this stabilises the tipping in question.

Table 1.2b lists the planned *TipESM* experiments. We aim to complete the *TipESM_core* simulations in the first 15 months of the project. Design and execution of the more targeted experiments, *TipESM_ensemble*, *TipESM_domain* and *TipESM_forced*, will occur in collaboration with WPs 2, 3, 4, 5 and 7.

Table 1.2b *TipESM experiments to investigate climate TPs and their impacts across the Earth system*

Experiment	Purpose	Investigated tipping elements/events	Model type	How
<i>TipESM_core</i>	Identify: occurrence of climate TPs, processes underpinning them and precursors of them; Investigate interactions between TPs and the impact of one TP on other domains of the Earth system; Assess the reversibility of triggered TPs.	All potential physical and biogeochemical TPs spanning terrestrial, marine, ice and atmosphere domains.	Coupled ESM	Following an agreed protocol (proposed for TIPMIP) sampling a range of idealised global warming overshoot, stabilisation and return scenarios.
<i>TipESM_ensemble</i>	Ensembles to (i) test the robustness and sensitivity of a TE; (ii) identify downstream and remote impacts of a TE.	AMOC/SPG Amazon/forest ; Ice sheet loss.	Coupled ESMs	Perturbed initial state ensemble for an identified TE at specific warming levels; simulation length ~30-70 years.
<i>TipESM_domain</i>	Identify domain-specific processes (including assessment of their robustness) that lead to a specific TE.	Ice sheets; Amazon dieback; Permafrost SPG collapse	Ice sheet models; Land veg models; ocean models	Sensitivity experiments sampling: resolution, parameterisations and process complexity.
<i>TipESM_forced</i>	Cascade of one TE on the potential for others; (De)stabilising interactions between tipping elements; Attribution of TE impacts.	Amazon dieback; Ice sheet loss; AMOC/SPG	Coupled ESMs	Modify vegetation types or land use; Modify climate drivers of Antarctic ice loss; Freshwater or salinity input to the North Atlantic.

b. Delivering new knowledge on climate TPs and their driving processes (WPs2&3)

Our first aim is to update the *abrupt change risk-catalogue* started in the EU-project OptimESM with findings from the TiPES, COMFORT and EPOC projects and complement the catalogue, for instance by adding new TPs in ocean and terrestrial biogeochemistry and analysing the new *TipESM_core* overshoot simulations. To identify tipping elements, we will improve the method pioneered in Drijfhout et al. (2015). The basis of this method is a set of scripts developed to identify special types of rare events in large datasets, such as searching for dark matter in nuclear physics, complemented with tailor-made statistical tests for final identification of TPs. We will also pioneer a Machine Learning (ML) algorithm (Bury et al 2021), testing it for a selected variable and if successful using it more widely.

Once search and attribution is complete, identified TPs will be analysed with a generic feedback method to identify causal chains in which feedbacks rapidly amplify, inducing tipping in specific elements. The results will provide feedback to WP1 for designing targeted experiments. We will make use of the dedicated component model experiments (*TipESM_domain*) to identify key processes that contribute to tipping. We will also analyse the robustness of TPs and links between driving processes and TPs based on the *TipESM_ensemble* runs. Findings will be complemented by analysis of observations to benchmark the models TPs and identify possible model biases that may increase, decrease or even prevent the occurrence of TPs in current ESMs.

Further, we will assess downstream teleconnections between tipping in key Earth system processes and atmospheric circulation, with a focus on extreme weather events and possible abrupt changes in their likelihood and distribution (*TipESM_ensemble*). These effects will be assessed using lagged regressions. The method of finding abrupt changes in extreme weather and changes in extreme value distribution needs development, although this has begun on OptimESM.

Lagged regression will also be used to find physical and biogeochemical drivers for threshold crossing in mean climate and weather extremes, associated with tipping in a range of ecological and societal systems, with particular focus on thresholds identified in WP6. An incremental change in the climate, e.g. an increase in warming from 2.0 to 2.1 K or a small increase in frequency of certain weather extremes, may cause a tipping of these systems. These climate thresholds can be very local and vary between different systems. We will put these local thresholds into a larger scale context, e.g. under what GWLs they will be exceeded and to which large scale climate changes are they linked.

Finally, we will investigate reversibility and hysteresis by looking at asymmetrical responses in physical and biogeochemical parameters. We will use the ramp-up, ramp-down phases of the *TipESM_core* runs as a basis for this and look at potential reversibility in: the North Atlantic and Arctic, including the SPG, sea ice, AMOC and ocean extremes, in vegetated regions including the Amazon and Sahel, in continental ice sheets, and in atmospheric phenomena.

c. Developing early warning indicators and assessing the risk for cascades of TPs across the Earth system (WPs4&5)

Previous EWIs, based on increasing strength and slower recovery of fluctuations when a tipping is approached, will be applied to the TPs identified in TipESM simulations (also CMIP6, OptimESM). Such changes in fluctuations are typically identified by a change in the lag-1 autocorrelation (AR1) coefficient or variance. As well as focusing on the better known TPs, we will also look for EWIs of so far unknown, or poorly studied, tipping elements. After applying existing EWIs, we will develop new early warning methods. First, we will use space-for-time substitution (e.g. Dakos et al, 2010) to gain insight from remote sensing data with fine spatial but poor temporal resolution and complement the analysis of precursors, by identifying key spatial patterns that may precede a TE. For example, patterns associated with large freshwater events, such as the Great Salinity Anomalies, could be warnings for a collapse of Labrador Sea convection, the SPG or AMOC. The second new method will explore the autoregressive-moving-average process (ARMA, Palma, 2016) modelling with time-dependent coefficients (tdARMA) and other related models, which may contain more types of memory than AR1. This approach enables calculation of a likelihood function, providing a stricter test of statistical significance.

The EWIs considered should be observable, meaning observations for the relevant variables exist, or it is realistic to expect these variables will be observable in the near future. This is important to ensure the EWIs we develop are useful in the real world. TipESM will provide important guidance for future TP observing systems.

Applying the specific EWIs to the ESMs will allow us to test their reliability. In particular, we will investigate the risk of false positives (i.e., when an EWI indicates a TP that does not happen) and how far in advance a TP can be predicted with reasonable skill. Ultimately, the EWIs will be applied to relevant observations to identify TPs that might already be approaching (for example WGIS, AMOC). Tipping or extreme events that trigger other TPs can also be interpreted as EWIs. The importance of understanding such cascades goes far beyond the use of the initial TP as a warning indicator, since it is particularly important for society to avoid TPs that trigger a cascade of events.

Such TP cascades are suggested by theoretical considerations and conceptual models. We will test these hypotheses in our ESMs, investigating the potential chain of proposed interactions. We will analyse both the *TipESM_core* and *TipESM_forced* experiments to understand this risk more fully. We focus on links between the GIS, WAIS and AMOC, as well as between changes in the North Atlantic Ocean circulation and atmospheric circulation, such as the West African Monsoon or Atlantic jet stream. The *TipESM_forced* experiments will allow us to investigate the impact of abrupt physical climate changes on marine and terrestrial biogeochemistry, carbon uptake and ecosystem functioning, complementing other North Atlantic water hosing experiments that focus only on physical processes. To separate the effect of exceeding TPs from other, more general, impacts of climate change, we will compare the *TipESM_forced* experiments with parallel non-tipping simulations for the respective TEs (Table 1.2b).

Finally, we will explore linkages between extreme climate events and TPs to assess the potential for a major extreme event to trigger different tipping elements in the Earth system. Such extremes might serve as early warning. We will begin with the TEs identified in the *TipESM_core* runs and scan backwards, using suitable detection methods, to determine if extreme events preceded a TE and if a causal relationship can be established. Second, we will focus on the potential for specific extreme events, such as atmosphere and marine heat waves, extended droughts, or oceanic freshwater and heat transports, to cause tipping in climate phenomena already known to be at risk. We will investigate if the risk of extreme events causing tipping in the climate system increases with the GWL, where the combination of potentially more frequent and stronger extremes, within a changed climatological (background) state that is potentially more vulnerable, leads to a greater risk of tipping.

d. Identifying climate-driven TPs in ecosystem and society (WP6)

Incremental warming and associated climate change, including changes in extreme events, may be an important risk for tipping in ecological and social systems. Such tipping may have important consequences for biodiversity, human habitability and activities (e.g. type of agriculture in a given region). To assess this risk, we focus on a range of individual ecosystems and investigate which local or large-scale climate conditions (or exceedance of climate thresholds) would lead to tipping in these ecosystems. We will use a chain of models, from full ESMs, offline ESM-component models and impact models (see Table 1.2c), to investigate ecosystems and social systems that are vulnerable due to their location and/or limited ability to migrate, for example poleward or to higher altitudes.

Terrestrial ecosystems

We focus on forest and savanna biomes in Sub-Saharan Africa, the Amazon rainforest, and mountain ecosystems. We will also investigate subsequent tipping in tree-dependent animal populations. We will initially use simulations and reconstructions of Holocene paleo vegetation and hydrology to understand underlying processes and thresholds that lead to tipping. The reconstructions include African pollen data, lake status data, and hydrological synthesis, and provide targeted criteria for model-data comparisons following the Paleoclimate Modeling Intercomparison Project (PMIP). To further investigate the sensitivity of tipping in vegetation, we will apply the land surface model ORCHIDEE from the IPSL-ESM. Similarities between past (paleo) TEs and those simulated by the TipESM models, particularly the *TipESM_domain* runs focused on forest dieback, will be assessed.

In addition, we will use biome and wildfire impact models from ISIMIP (Frieler et al. 2023) and observation-based data of the best-sampled African animal taxon (observations with high spatial and temporal coverage), in particular the IUCN SSC Ape Populations, Environments and Surveys (A.P.E.S.) database (Heinicke et al., 2019). In this case, we define the crossing of a TP when changes in climate conditions first lead to tipping from forest to savanna and, as a consequence, changes in forest cover lead to the local extirpation of apes. The differing degree of tree-dependence allows for a cross-taxa comparison and furthering our process-understanding of TPs. Finally, a modified version of the BIOME4 model (Kaplan et al. 2003) to quantify the spatial extent of all mountain habitats will be used. BIOME4 will be run for selected mountain ranges at a 1 km resolution using climate forcing from ISIMIP3, downscaled with CHELSA (Karger et al., 2022). We will quantify the biodiversity of different species groups (e.g. mammals, amphibians, reptiles, plants) based on occurrence data from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and literature information. Changes in biodiversity will be modelled using a species-area-environment model (SAER).

Marine ecosystems

Gradual and abrupt changes associated with deoxygenation, acidification, and nutrient redistribution have cascading impacts on marine ecosystems and might lead to their tipping. One focus will be on marine habitats for selected commercial fish species. Based on CMIP6 output and TipESM simulations, we will calculate a range of ecosystem metrics, such as thermal tolerance, metabolic index (Deutsch et al. 2015), and aerobic growth index (Clarke et al. 2021). We will evaluate the marine habitat loss and eventual extinction risk in response to gradual and abrupt changes, in particular in regions vulnerable to deoxygenation and acidification, such as the tropical Pacific, Arctic Ocean, upwelling areas, or deep sea habitats. Our second focus will be on fjord systems in Greenland, investigating thresholds at which changes in ocean stratification and retreat of marine terminating glaciers might lead to TEs in local fish populations. Local, fjord-scale *in situ* observations will be integrated with ESM model output and observed glacial retreat rates to give guidance on future glacier grounding lines. Catch records will be explored in the context of physical indicators to qualify potential societal impacts. Using existing literature, we will identify climate and sea ice conditions under which Arctic zooplankton and ice algae are likely to tip. This could be the result of regional, or Arctic-wide, disappearance of sea ice and have significant consequences for higher trophic levels (e.g. fish, whales, birds, polar bears).

Social systems

Following Milkoreit et al. (2018), we define a social TP as a point within a social-ecological system at which a small quantitative change triggers a non-linear change in the social component of the system, driven by self-reinforcing positive-feedback mechanisms that leads to a qualitatively different, potentially irreversible, state of the social system. As a case study, we consider the impact of recurrent tropical cyclones on households in the Philippines. Here a social TP is passed when households on average cannot recover between storms. This threshold depends on the (nonlinear) interplay of the households' recovery dynamics and changes in return frequency and intensity of the storm events. Since poorer households are often more exposed and have less means to recover, they have a lower threshold and a higher risk of being trapped in poverty (Walsh and Hallegatte 2020). We will combine a novel tropical cyclone emulator (Geiger et al. 2021), a storm surge model based on the shallow water equation solver GeoClaw (Mandli and Dawson 2014), and an agent-based model for the recovery dynamics of households to better understand the poverty implications of recurrent tropical-cyclone induced flooding under climate change in the Philippines, one of the most

tropical-cyclone prone developing countries. This pioneering study can serve as a proof of concept for subsequent application to other regions of the world.

Table 1.2c Impact models used in TipESM and the application

Model (reference)	Model Description	Realm/ Processes	Application in the TipESM (Task where the model applied)
BIOME4 (Kaplan et al, 2003)	Equilibrium global vegetation model based on 1km outputs from CHELSA-ISIMIP3b	Global Mountains	TPs of global mountain biodiversity (Task6.1)
ECO-Spillv.1.2*	Adaptive Network Model coupled to SEIR model	Health/Zoonotic spillovers	Changes in probability of spillover due to dieback of rainforests (Task7.5)
HBM (Andrée et al. 2021)	Storm surge model with forcing from climate model simulations	Storm surge	Changes in frequency of compound flooding events with storm surge and pluvial flooding (Task7.2)
ISIMIP3 impact models (Frieler et al. 2023)	Climate impact models from ISIMIP3b based on a cross-sectorially harmonise modelling protocol	1. Forests in Sub-Saharan Africa; 2. Flood hazards & Displacement; 3. Flooding & poverty traps.	1. Tipping in forest cover; 2. Storms and floods change leading to tipping in social system; 3. Flooding frequency change leading to tipping to persistent poverty (Task6.1 & Task6.3)
JULES-ES for ISIMIP (Mathison et al, 2023)	Land surface model, setup in a configuration relevant to assess climate impacts.	Land-atm. interactions for 1) carbon, water and nitrogen cycles; 2) food-water-energy interactions	Consequences of tipping on food and water systems (Task7.1&7.3)
LPJ-GUESS modified (β version Github)	Global dynamic vegetation-ecosystem model coupled to a moisture tracking model	Ecosystem/ Amazon	Type of forest cover among matrix and core species in the Amazon and potential dieback associated with ENSO changes (Task6.1)
ORCHIDEE *	Impact model from IPSL-ESM land surface component with a dynamical vegetation module	Paleo, savanna-forest and northern Europe tree line	Tipping Sahel-Sahara boundary and East/west Africa effects on vegetation & hydrology (Task6.1)
SAER*	Species area environment model based on CLM5 and BIOME4 outputs from ISIMIP3b	Global Mountains	TPs of global mountain biodiversity (Task 6.1)
VIC3** + ELEVMal Malaria ***	Process-based models of malaria dynamics	Malaria	Changes in distribution and incidence of malaria in the fringes (Task 7.5)

* version in development. ** Laneri et al., 2015. *** Rodó et al., 2021.

In a second application of social tipping, we will study the implications of changing frequency of flood hazard for human displacement. Again, a social TP is exceeded when disaster-induced displacement starts to become permanent because the time between disasters is shorter than (or on the same order as) the time required to recover from a given disaster. We will use estimates of average displacement duration, based on expected damage and recovery times as a function of flood depth, to characterise the displacement duration of past events. We will then employ spatially explicit future projections of flood hazard from tropical cyclone storm surges - using the methodology mentioned above - as well as river flooding using the global model CaMa-Flood (Yamazaki et al., 2011) to quantify changes in the average return intervals between flood events under future climate change. Based on these findings, we will identify areas where temporary human displacement might become permanent. Because habitability depends not only on exposure to a physical hazard, but also on the adaptive capacity of the exposed population (Horton et al.,

2021), our analysis will take into account the estimated local vulnerability to displacement, based on past events, as well as future changes in socio-economic characteristics according to the Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs; KC & Lutz, 2017).

e. Delivering new knowledge on the impacts of TPs on ecosystem and society (WP7)

We will run and further develop existing impact models to analyse multi-sectoral impacts arising due to crossing climate TPs (see Table 1.2c). The exact focus of our analysis depends on the TPs identified in the range of TipESM simulations, with output from these simulations providing climate forcing (across a climate TE, and its counterfactual, non-tipping simulation; *TipESM_forced* runs) for the impact models. In addition, we will investigate the compound and cascading impacts resulting from abrupt ice sheet loss, sea level rise and a potential increase in the likelihood and intensity of storm surges with impacts on coastal regions. We will also investigate the impact of, TP induced increases in temperature and humidity, as well as changes in the seasonal cycle for heat stress feedback, fire and drought.

To better interconnect food systems and water security and assess their joint sensitivity to climate tipping, we will implement in the JULES land model key elements, such as crop suitability and yield, river flooding and over-bank inundation, and water storage for energy production and human consumption. We will analyse the suitability of climate, after crossing TPs, for human habitation, including the impact of heat stress. We focus on geographical spread and the timing of transition towards the critical heat stress conditions for different global warming and TP scenarios. Work will distinguish heat stress impacts between urban and rural areas and consider interactions between climate tipping and urban heat island in JULES. It will also integrate aspects of livestock physiology and crop failure due to heat to estimate the overall impacts on human migration, demographics and habitability.

Climate tipping and related regional climate change may have impact the distribution of infectious diseases. For example, tipping of the Sahel/West African monsoon, as a response to drastic changes in the AMOC and/or an ice free Arctic, might affect malaria incidence and propagation in the subtropical belt and semi-desert areas, as well as expansion in high altitudes (Laneri et al. 2015, Rodó et al. 2021). Tipping of GIS and Arctic winter sea ice may have a dramatic impact on the hydrological cycle, impacting diarrhea diseases worldwide, in particular in tropical Africa and the Indian subcontinent. TipESM aims to quantify the effect of climate tipping on the distribution of infectious diseases and global range of their vectors. To investigate impacts on global malaria distribution, we will use a nested version of our VIC3 ISGlobal malaria model for desert-fringe areas and the ELEVMal model for highlands, to assess how the TipESM ESMs projections, with climate TEs, impact malaria propagation in latitudinal and altitudinal fringes of Africa.

A third focus will analyse how different TPs may induce risks for pathogen spillover due to dieback of the Amazon and African rainforests, using the *TipESM_domain* experiments, combined with a modified version of LPJ-GUESS and a moisture tracking model to determine both types of forest cover among matrix and core species (Staal et al., 2020). We will then explore probabilistic simulations of ECO-Spillv.1.2 (forced by *TipESM_ensemble* data) for assessing changes in both frequency and intensity of zoonotic spillover in the Amazon. We will provide an assessment of the key parameter space trajectories, which result in collapse of present day ecosystems and the consequences of these under the different TipESMs scenarios.

f. Constraining future TP risks and providing safe mitigation emission pathways (WP8)

We will begin by building on existing emergent constraint approaches by using advanced statistical methods. We aim to reduce uncertainty in model projections of key climate variables, associated with tipping events. Emergent constraints relate model projections of the future sensitivity of a particular variable to observable (historical) sensitivities/variability of the same variable, across an ensemble of ESMs, and then exploit this relationship to constrain the future sensitivity (in the ESMs) based on which ESMs most accurately captures the past (observed) variability in the associated variable (Cox et al. 2013, Eyring et al. 2019). The fidelity of an emergent constraint depends classically on the correlation of the relationship and the uncertainty of the observations. Emergent constraints have been applied many climate variables, such as transient and equilibrium climate sensitivity, the snow albedo feedback, carbon cycle feedbacks, marine primary production, Arctic Ocean acidification and Southern Ocean carbon uptake. However, emergent constraints are often based on one single predictor and linear regressions, and have rarely been applied to TPs, with some exceptions (Sgubin et al. 2017). Some first attempts have been made to apply this concept to tipping of the North Atlantic subpolar gyre using mean ocean stratification as a predictor. We propose to improve this type of empirical method by using several predictors for a given variable we wish to constrain in the future (related to a tipping element) and also use non-linear AI approaches for regression (e.g. Schlund et al. 2020).

The resulting TP emergent constraints will be important input to the TipESM risk register. The risk of climate hazards will be assessed by combining the likelihood of TPs in the model ensemble, combined with robustness in terms of irreversibility in ramp-up ramp-down runs (*TipESM_core*), stability in long stabilisation runs (*TipESM_core*), and in

experiments with forced tipping (*TipESM_forced*). Combined with a likelihood assessment based on tipping in multi-model, large ensemble runs (*TipESM_ensemble*), this will inform us on the likelihood of tipping in the model world. By comparing model biases and their relation to tipping in model runs, observational constraints from present-day and paleo-observations will be used to weight the model-derived likelihood towards more realistic models and adjust our overall assessment of the likelihood of tipping. This will be combined with an assessment of impacts, including exposure and vulnerability, taking into account the relation between tipping in natural and human systems and its sensitivity to exceeding certain climate/biogeochemical thresholds, including changes in weather extremes. These results will be synthesised in the same way as in the IPCC AR6-WGII report (Pörtner et al., 2022), in particular using Reasons For Concern (RFC) levels and burning embers, but now connecting these not via temperature thresholds *per se*, but *via* temperature thresholds associated with TEs. We anticipate not only updating information in the AR6-WGII report, but also complementing it with RFCs targeted at TPs and their impact, connecting TPs to the risk-landscape used in the IPCC reports. Following AR6-WGII we define risk as the potential for adverse consequences for human or ecological systems, recognising the diversity of values and objectives associated with such systems. This work will be synthesised in our project risk-register.

To inform stakeholders on safe emission pathways that minimise the risk of crossing individual TPs, we will develop novel adaptive emissions pathways. CMIP scenarios, with concentration or emissions pathways prescribed *a priori*, regardless of the simulated climate response, are not ideal to ensure avoiding crossing TPs. Hence, a model with a large transient climate response would likely exceed a TP threshold, while a model with a low transient climate response might remain below it. In TipESM, we will go beyond this by developing new adaptive emissions scenarios where emissions are adapted iteratively every 5 years, allowing for dynamic adjustments based on realised warming and the proximity to TPs. For example, a large rate of warming or a large decrease in AMOC would require implementing deeper emission reductions, conversely a moderate rate of warming or a small change in AMOC would allow for a slower rate of emission cuts. The adaptive process mimics the global stocktake process initiated by the Paris Agreement and also considers TPs and critical thresholds, not just GWLs (Terhaar et al. 2022). By taking this approach, combined with our new emergent constraints, we will provide our best estimate of the pathway and remaining carbon budget to minimise the chance of crossing certain Earth system TP thresholds, including extreme and compound event thresholds. We will first test the modified adaptive emissions reductions scenarios with the reduced complexity climate models Bern3D-LPX (Lienert and Joos 2018) and the Finite amplitude Impulse Response model (FaIR; Smith et al. 2018), before running these adaptive scenarios with a selected set of TipESM ESMs and a selected set of TPs. Both will be run under different configurations (e.g., ocean mixing, climate sensitivity) to test the sensitivity of the adaptive scenarios to uncertainties in the modelled climate response.

g. Supporting European climate policy (WPs9&10)

A key aim of TipESM is to maintain a regular two-way dialogue with European policy makers to ensure the research we carry out is both informed by, and supports, policy needs. To achieve this, we will create a number of focus groups comprising EU and national policymakers to listen to the requirements of these groups and provide information on important project findings. Based on these discussions, where possible we will modify our plans to ensure major project simulations, analyses and findings deliver useful and actionable information into the policy arena. We will also work with the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) to investigate whether our simulations are of interest to the broader European landscape of climate policy and climate services. Wherever this is the case we will endeavour to make such data available to the C3S service.

An important outcome will be the TipESM TPs risk register, providing policymakers and stakeholders with unique information on the likelihood of crossing individual TPs at various GWLs and the consequences of such tipping events for ecosystems and society. This risk register will be complemented with safe emission pathways that minimise the likelihood of crossing individual TPs, directly supporting European policy. TipESM will further develop new EWIs for TPs and provide guidance for future observational systems aimed at detecting early warning of a TP. TipESM will also ensure a strong dialogue with the impacts modelling community, building on links developed in previous and ongoing European projects (e.g. CRESCENDO, ESM2025, OptimESM) and our involvement in ISIMIP. We will organise workshops to discuss science and data requirements, ensuring an efficient flow of data and knowledge between the project and this community. A similar interaction will be maintained with the CORDEX regional climate downscaling community. We will cluster with other European projects and international activities (e.g. TIPMIP) to provide consistent and coherent information to policymakers. Finally, we will ensure the main project findings are regularly communicated to the European public through engagement in science festivals, researcher nights, direct contact with local community and school groups and *via* active use of social media.

1.2.2 Links to national and international research

TipESM will cooperate closely with relevant national and European projects and link its work to major international programmes. TipESM will also benefit from work done in recently concluded projects. Consortium members of TipESM have/had leading positions in many of these projects. The ESMs in TipESM include recent improvements

Box 2: TIPMIP – The Tipping Points Model Intercomparison Project

The Tipping Points Model Intercomparison Project (TIPMIP) is an initiative led by Ricarda Winkelmann and colleagues at the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK) and the Earth Commission, and was officially launched in September 2022. TIPMIP will systematically investigate tipping points in the climate system, using Earth System Models as well as stand-alone models. In phase 1, TIPMIP will focus on tipping points of the two ice sheets on Greenland and Antarctica, the AMOC, permafrost as well as the boreal and tropical forests. A set of four experiments is planned: (1) a *baseline* experiment, simulating historic change and the projected response of the tipping elements to climate and land-use change scenarios; (2) a *commitment* experiment, assessing the centennial to millennial impacts of prolonging certain CO₂ levels in the atmosphere; (3) a *reversibility* experiment, assessing whether (and if so, on which timescales) certain impacts are reversible; and (4) a *rate-induced tipping* experiment, probing the role of the forcing rate for the impacts on each of the tipping elements. In phase 2 of TIPMIP, it is planned to extend the number of tipping elements, and to include a *noise-induced tipping* experiment. As apparent from the experimental protocol, there are a number of strong links between TipESM and TIPMIP. TipESM would form an important contribution to the ESM simulations for the intercomparison – in turn, TipESM would benefit from TIPMIP through additional simulations with further ESMs as well as the stand-alone simulations which allow for a deeper process-understanding and a larger simulation ensemble. The TIPMIP leader Ricarda Winkelmann will be a member of the TipESM External Advisory Board to facilitate the TipESM –

made in the EU-projects **CRESCENDO** and **ESM2025** to a number of model components, such as the land surface, vegetation, carbon, methane and nitrogen cycles, interactive ice sheets and OBGC, all highly relevant for the simulation of TPs. Throughout the project, TipESM will work closely with **OptimESM**. It will use ESM simulations performed in OptimESM for the analysis of TPs, and will extend the OptimESM protocol to include a larger set of ESMs, with the aim of providing an internationally-accepted ESM protocol for WCRP/FutureEarth TIPMIP (Box 2).

To reach our specific objectives, TipESM will build on the legacy of **COMFORT**, **TipES**, **TipACCs** and **PROTECT**. Comparing the occurrence and impact of TPs from conceptual models, single component models and coupled physical models with our results based on full ESMs will provide important new knowledge on the role of feedbacks across the Earth system for TP risks and consequences. TipESM will closely connect to the WCRP/FutureEarth **TIPMIP** and to the **North Atlantic Hosing MIP** (NAHosMIP), complementing and extending these activities through use of fully coupled ESMs. Further, TipESM will align with the EU-projects **AMOC-NEXT**, **EPOC** and **OCEAN:ICE** around processes driving the AMOC and the two-way impact between AMOC and human activities. TipESM will also connect with the **AtlantECO** project when assessing the Atlantic Ocean and its ecosystem response to climate change as well as with **PROVIDE** when assessing the reversibility and irreversibility of TP impacts.

For investigation of subpolar and polar processes driving abrupt change, we will benefit from the understanding, model improvements and observations in polar projects such as **Blue-Action**, **APPLICATE**, **INTAROS**, **ArcticPassion** and **CRiceS**. TipESM will also benefit from developments in European technical infrastructure made in **IS-ENES3** and **ESiWACE2**, and will work with the new **ESiWACE3** project to address computational challenges associated with the increased complexity and interactivity of the latest ESMs. TipESM will also benefit from outputs of **RECEIPT**, on damages caused by climate hazards, and methodological developments in modelling displacement from **HABITABLE**.

TipESM will closely align with certain national projects such as the **Danish National Centre for Climate Research** (NCKF) supporting Earth system modelling and research on climate change and impacts; the UK Earth system modelling project, the UK-project **TerraFIRMA** (involving eight NERC centres and the Met Office Hadley Centre) and the Met Office Hadley Centre Climate Programme (**HCCP**); the Swedish project **FutureGS** on the Gulf Stream in a warming climate; the **Dutch Polar Climate and Cryosphere Change Consortium** mapping current and future changes in polar regions and the **Dutch MSO**-project that couples an ice sheet model to EC-Earth to investigate future Antarctic contribution to sea level rise; the German project **QUIDIC** on costs of climate-related hazards and

the DFG project **CCH2** on climate change and health in Africa. It will also benefit from the French programme **TRACCS**, which funds development of French ESMs for the next 8 years, and assists links with relevant climate services. Results from the project will contribute to several arboviral diseases prediction platforms in ISGlobal, for the Mediterranean and Thailand through **ARBOTHAI**, a Wellcome Trust Grant for Climate-sensitive diseases modelling, and inform malaria and diarrheal disease alert systems building resilience to emerging health threats and, ADAPT, German Federal Ministry of Education and Research, BMBF, 01KA2218B, as well as the African One Health Network for Disease Prevention and PREZODE (Preventing ZOonotic Disease Emergence) international network.

TipESM will work closely with other ESM-centres, particularly in the North America, Japan, India and South Africa, to help pave the way towards CMIP7 and share model improvements and simulation data (see Table 1.2d). TipESM will also work closely with two unfunded EU partners: Meteo France who will contribute to TipESM simulations with the CNRM-ESM, and the Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (CNR-ISAC), Italy, who will contribute to the TP analysis in WP2 and WP3.

Table 1.2d European and International Partners of TipESM

Partner Institution	Main contact point	How TipESM benefits via clustering activity
NCAR (USA)	Gokhan Danabasoglu	Development of the ESM protocol <i>TipESM_core</i> , and possible realisation of experiments with CESM; Sharing of analysis methods and results.
NOAA-GFDL (USA)	John Dunne	Development of the ESM protocol <i>TipESM_core</i> , and possible realisation of experiments with the newest GFDL-ESM; Sharing of analysis methods and results.
JAMSTEC (Japan)	Michio Kawamiya	Development of the ESM protocol <i>TipESM_core</i> , and possible realisation of experiments with MIROC-ESM; Sharing of analysis methods and results.
IITM (India)	Krishnan Raghavan	Development of the ESM protocol <i>TipESM_core</i> , and possible realisation of experiments with IITM-ESM; Sharing of analysis methods and results.
Wits University (South Africa)	Francois Engelbrecht	Analysis of TipESM simulations for understanding the regional impacts.
Meteo France (France)	Roland Séférian	Development of the ESM protocol <i>TipESM_core</i> , and possible realisation of these experiments with CNRM-ESM.
CNR-ISAC (Italy)	Susanna Corti	Participate in development of catalogue of TPs in the climate system, analysis of reversibility of TPs and rare extreme events in trigger TPs, as well as the synthesis results for risk registers.

Links to other initiatives

TipESM is aligned with the EU’s Missions “Adaptation to Climate Change”, “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” and “Climate Neutral and Smart Cities” where the ambitions are for a “societal transition towards a climate neutral and climate resilient society by 2030, as well as towards a more ambitious greenhouse gas reduction target by 2030”. TipESM will contribute knowledge on TPs risks and potential shocks to climate, ecosystems and society that will help design mitigation and adaptation policies that minimise risk and reduce exposure. The PO will establish links to the mission and explore ways TipESM outputs can complement activities under the mission mandate. TipESM will engage with the **European Environmental Agency’s ClimateAdapt** platform to disseminate our results in a coordinated manner and further enhance exploitation of the project outcomes. Lastly, to avoid duplication and maximise exploitation, we will coordinate with Copernicus Climate Change Services and the Climate Data Store. This link will be particularly relevant to our activities under Open Science (§1.2.6).

TipESM contributes to the **WCRP lighthouse activities**, particularly to *Safe Landing Climates* where TipESM contributes directly to all five of the main science themes, and to *Explaining and Predicting Earth system change and Digital Earth*. We will ensure our simulation plans are informed by priorities in the various lighthouses and maintain a regular dialogue with each of these activities. TipESM will also ensure a strong European leadership in **CMIP7** by directly involving six state-of-the-art ESMs. The high standing of TipESM consortium members (see

§3.2) will ensure our work influences other international climate and Earth system science bodies, supporting future UNFCCC, WMO, WCRP, IPCC, FutureEarth, AMAP and other regional and national assessments. TipESM partners have significant experience as IPCC authors in AR4, AR5, SR15 and SCOCC, and have contributed as lead-/contributing authors to AR6 (see also §3.2). TipESM partners include former and recent steering and committee members of e.g. the WCRP-WGCM, WCRP-WGNE, WCRP-WWRP, WCRP-SLC, WCRP-CORDEX, WCRP Joint Scientific Committee (JSC), WCRP marine heatwave research focus, NEMO-consortium, and steering group members and co-chair of the Ice Sheet Model Intercomparison Project 6 (ISMIP6,) as well as Executive committee member of the Ice sheet Mass Balance Inter-Comparison Exercise (IMBIE).

Through involvement in these bodies we will help shape future priorities in Earth system modelling, scenario development, climate services, climate impact assessment and science-policy interaction.

Clustering with sister projects and the HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-02

In addition to the activities described above, TipESM will collaborate with, complement, and support sister projects funded under the same call and with projects funded under the topic HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-02 on the development of community-based research infrastructures. While our project does not have any critical dependencies with other projects under this call, we have held discussions with one other consortium developing a proposal and have agreed on three areas for cooperation should both projects be funded. These are: scientific research, stakeholder networks and user interactions, and dissemination/ exploitation/ communication. Several actions are proposed. We see the potential for joint meetings, including one at the beginning of the projects to identify synergies and reduce duplication, and joint science meetings to share learning and results at the middle and end of the projects (most likely coincident with General Assemblies). User and stakeholder networks will be shared and collaboration around co-production envisioned where practicable. The projects will also collaborate on communication to be consistent, more impactful, and have greater reach. The two projects will also explore the possibility to hold a joint Science2Policy event towards the end of their project periods, which could be undertaken with involvement of relevant Coordination and Support Actions. Regular contact between the project coordination teams is envisioned.

1.2.3 Importance of multidisciplinary approach in TipESM

TipESM follows a multidisciplinary approach to ensure a comprehensive modelling and understanding of TPs and their consequences across the Earth system. This is evidenced by inclusion in the project of researchers from different disciplines working together to integrate knowledge and methods from across these disciplines. TipESM will build a close collaboration between researchers in a range of natural sciences, such as climate, ocean, atmosphere, cryosphere, biogeochemistry, biology, health, as well as groups expert in integrated assessment and ecological and societal impacts. Such a multi-disciplinary team enables modelling of climate TPs and climate-driven ecosystem and societal tippings (SO6, SO7), as well as investigation of potential interactions and cascades across the Earth system (SO1-SO5). It provides the basis for development of safe mitigation pathways to avoid critical TP thresholds in Earth system (SO8).

1.2.4 Role of social sciences and humanities in TipESM

TipESM moves beyond the state-of-the-art in critical areas of climate and social sciences as well as efforts to connect the two. These ambitions are key to meeting our specific objectives and ensuring impact of the project. We divide them into those related to fundamental science and those related to knowledge co-production, aligning with the overall conceptualisation of the project and the associated work-plan. TipESM envisages:

- combining climate and social sciences using a two-way approach. WP6 includes quantification of climatic conditions that lead to tipping in eco- and societal systems, and WP7 quantifies the impact of climate tipping on ecosystems stability and aspects of society and human health. This will further the integration of ESMs and climate impact models. WP6 also addresses the efficiency of different adaptation measures to climate change impacts, of high relevant for society and policy-makers.
- the inclusion of social scientists will allow a rigorous co-production process as the project transforms data to information, information to knowledge and delivers this knowledge to society.
- support to target groups in better designing adaptation strategies and delineating safe scenarios, to avoid unmanageable impacts and cascade onto ecosystems and societies.

1.2.5 Gender dimension

In TipESM gender (i.e. sex and/or gender analysis) encompassing both biological characteristics and social/cultural factors has been taken into account in the design of project's research and innovation content, using the Yellow Window Gender Checklist and the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE). Gender effects people in terms of engaging with emerging threats from climate change and mitigation measures are taken into account in WP 6, 7 and 8. Specifically in WP6, TipESM will focus on poor households, poverty traps and adaptation measures to extreme

weather events, all particularly relevant for women. Gender is particularly relevant in climate protection policies, specifically in the design and implementation of adaptation and mitigation strategies. TipESM will consider the various gender-related aspects of climate change: the impact of climate change on women and men; their different contributions to and perceptions of climate change; and the solutions that women and men are perceived to prefer in terms of mitigation and adaptation. Gender differences regarding impacts of climate change will be accounted for: such as more women casualties during extreme weather events and an increased burden from care work, as well as evidence of gender specific consumption patterns that affect greenhouse gas emissions, gender specific mobility patterns and greater risk of energy poverty in women and so fewer options for investing in low-carbon options such as energy efficiency and renewable energies. TipESM will also consider the intersectionality with other factors and avoid disaggregating data by sex – viewing women as an undifferentiated group and opposing this to men as an undifferentiated group. Consideration of gender will be integrated throughout WP9-10. Gender balance in the research team is described in §3.2.

1.2.6 Open Science

TipESM has Open Science (OS) practices as an integral part of its proposed methodology and work plan: WP9-10 sets the framework for OS management by coordinating a data management plan (DMP), FAIR data management practices, OS publishing and coordinates OS related dissemination and exploitation. Project data and publications will be open access, including access to research output and tools (e.g., modified AERA code and emergent constraint toolbox), by actively using the Horizon Results Platform to share Key Exploitable Results. In addition, TipESM will engage in several recommended OS practices:

1. Early and open sharing of research output, through publishing in journals which perform open peer review and online-publishing of submitted manuscripts, such as the Copernicus-journals (no hybrids); open science dissemination management to guide and train project researchers and increase accessibility and findability of our publications.
2. Open access to research output through deposition of data in trusted repositories; see draft DMP (§1.2.7).
3. Engaging relevant knowledge actors in co-creating an R&I agenda and content through co-design and co-production. We will target relevant users and stakeholders through the Stakeholder Reference Group (Task 9.3 and task 10.3), as well as civil society through discussions at specific events (Task 9.1 and task 10.1).
4. Results will be published in open access repositories and/or as annexes to publications.
5. TipESM will guarantee full openness of any new models or tools developed or improved through EU funding.
6. TipESM will take into account relevant initiatives for ensuring the quality of scientific software and link to projects funded under the topic HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-02 on community-based approaches.

1.2.7 Data management

Data management will be linked to our Open Science goals and exploitation plans. Led by DMI, TipESM dedicates tasks T9.4 and T10.4 for managing data. The objective of TipESM's data management strategy will be to promote sustainability and successful dissemination of project results. Data management will be implemented on the following principles: 1) All data will be managed to the highest standards as part of the consortium's commitment to research excellence; 2) Data will be available for access and re-use under appropriate safeguards; 3) The consortium will provide all necessary information to make sure results generated in TipESM will be reproducible. A data management panel will be formed at the kick off meeting consisting of one participant for each WP and the data manager, and will report to the steering committee. The data policy will be supervised by the project office. A data management plan (DMP) will be delivered in month 6 and revised three times during the project (D9.3, D9.6, D9.8, D10.4). The majority of data generated will output from ESM simulations. This data will be in NetCDF format, with in-file annotation following CMIP conventions. TipESM will establish a repository at the IPSL computing centre (ESPRI) for data sharing and analysis within the project, and when appropriate, sharing with the broader scientific community on other open access repositories (e.g., GitHub, Zenodo, ESGF). ESPRI is experienced in data management and hosts climate data produced by CNRS as well as many national and EU projects (e.g., ESM2025), providing open access to scientists worldwide and offering a range of services on data quality, uniform formatting, simplifying use and comparison with other data. The project simulation data will be stored on the ESGF beyond the project end. Full sets of data will also be stored on local institutional archives.

The DMP will identify other data generated in the project, such as documents, figures and animations for dissemination (e.g., Zenodo). The DMP will also outline which data will be openly shared with the scientific community and when. The aim is to make use, wherever possible, of open access repositories. The DMP will encompass information on how data will be handled during and after the end of the project by providing an analysis of the Data Management policy to be applied by the partners, linked to the exploitation plan. The DMP will be followed throughout the project and will be interconnected with the exploitation and dissemination activities to pave

the way for post-project exploitation. An integrated approach will be followed for the identification, capture, retrieval, distribution, sharing, use and reuse of TipESM data. Individual partners will be responsible for providing the necessary mechanisms and services for local storage, backup, confidentiality, retention, sharing, and publication of the raw project datasets.

Table 1.2e How TipESM ensures that FAIR principles are adhered to.

Findability	ESM simulations will be made available on the ESGF and the project repository at ESPRI for sharing with TipESM partners; where appropriate datasets from WP2-8 will be made discoverable via appropriate platforms and/or the repository ESPRI.
Accessibility	All articles will be open access, data will be openly available; licences for data use, software, etc. will follow CC BY 4.0 “unrestricted”; all metadata will follow CC 0; Data will be made available open access via trusted data repositories (ESGF, ESPRI, partner HPC & storage).
Interoperability	The data space at ESPRI offers Virtual Research Environments (VRE) that can be replicated (e.g., using Conda or Singularity), ensuring platform interoperability. The open tools developed will be based free software languages (e.g., R and Python). Standards will be used (and developed, e.g. Task 3.4) favouring interoperability and cooperation. In particular, standard machine-readable formats with metadata will be used for all data.
Reusability	The ESM experiment protocols (WP1) available as peer-reviewed publication or online (Zenodo). The document for Emergent Constraint Toolbox and AERA code (WP8) and documentation made available via GitHub and/or Zenodo.

2. Impact

TipESM will deliver a unique contribution to the climate research landscape through advancing our knowledge on the risk of climate TPs and their potential impact on ecological systems and society. TP research provides horizon scanning and early warning for future risks and shocks to the interconnected environment, society and economy. As the EU transforms its economy for a sustainable future (Green Deal) and moves to a climate resilient Europe it is essential to prepare for threats and disasters, understand risks to infrastructure and current net zero pathways, and the capacity of natural systems and ecosystem services to cope with abrupt changes. In section 2 we identify how TipESM addresses the work programme and the expected outcomes and impacts (§2.1) and maximises impact through dissemination, communication and exploitation (§2.2).

2.1 TipESM’s pathways towards impact

2.1.1 Contributing to the expected outcomes and impacts

Table 2.1 Pathways to impact: The unique contributions TipESM will make to the expected outcomes (EO) and impacts (EI). See also the Summary Table 2.3 Impact Canvas.

#EO1 New or improved models for climate predictions or projections which take into account climate-related potential TPs and their impacts, and are relevant for major assessments e.g. IPCC and IPBES.
TipESM will deploy the latest ESMs with recent improvements in key processes, including interactive ice sheets, dynamic vegetation, marine biogeochemistry, permafrost, and atmospheric chemistry, enabling closed cycles of water, carbon, methane and nitrogen, to realise simulations that underpin a series of analyses: the likelihood of different TPs occurring, their potential (ir)reversibility, the robustness of TPs across ESMs. TipESM will reduce uncertainties associated with crossing future TPs by developing and employing an emergent constraint toolbox using AI methods. TipESM will expand knowledge of potential TPs, their drivers and tipping-related thresholds in ecological and societal areas, making a significant contribution to the next IPCC and IPBES assessments. (SO1, SO2, SO3, SO7, SO8)
#EO2 Better understanding of potential compound or cascading effects on climate, ecosystems and society as a consequence of crossing specific TPs.

TipESM will investigate and identify important cascading and compound events and analyse their significance. The project will examine the impact of potential cascades that could lead to, e.g., storm surges and coastal impacts, extinction events, wildfires and droughts. If triggered, TP impacts can rapidly cascade through ecological systems and society, leading to severe effects on human and natural systems and important challenges for adaptation (OECD). New knowledge on cascading effects will inform policy in developing risk management strategies and provide information on how TEs may impact the realisation of the UN sustainable development goals. (SO3, SO4, SO5, SO6, SO7)

#EO3 Increased capacity to identify unknown tipping elements and early warning signals when a TP is approached

TipESM will enhance our ability to identify early warning signals of tipping events. Simulations with the latest ESMs provide the opportunity to identify potential, unknown tipping elements in the ocean, atmosphere, cryosphere, land and vegetation. The warming overshoot and stabilisation experiments will provide a unique data set to improve our understanding of both known and unknown tipping elements and their sensitivity to global warming. TipESM will assess existing, and develop new, early warning indicators and provide guidance on priorities for future observational networks to detect early warning signals of potential TEs. (SO2, SO3, SO4, SO5)

#EO4 Contribution to mitigation policies with regard to the Paris Agreement and the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, taking into account the precautionary principle, with respect to abrupt responses, hysteresis and other non-linear behaviour of the Earth system.

The World Economic Forum ranks a “Failure to mitigate climate change” as one of the most severe short-term threats to the planet. This assessment does not take into account that several TPs may be crossed under current policy trajectories (Lenton et al., 2019). TipESM will synthesise project results into a risk register of future TPs to provide insight into the hazards, vulnerability, and exposure associated with crossing climate, ecosystem and societal TPs. Results and simulations from TipESM will be linked to research addressing global biodiversity risks. The project will quantify the risk of triggering TEs as a function of the magnitude and length of time global warming is above the Paris goals and explore novel adaptive emission scenarios to quantify safe mitigation pathways. These pathways can be revised every 5 years in the light of realised warming and proximity to a TP. For the first time, a best estimate of the pathway and remaining carbon budget to minimise the likelihood of crossing TPs in the Earth system will be made. This knowledge will inform EU policies to prepare for disruptions to the environment, society and the economy, understand trade-offs and ensure Europe is as climate resilient as possible. (SO6, SO7, SO8, SO9)

#EO5 Input to adaptation strategies for the most affected regions, globally, addressing the risks of crossing climatic TPs and related impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity.

Taking into account climate TPs is crucial for a comprehensive analysis of climate risk to inform mitigation pathways and for effective adaptation design and implementation. TipESM will push the frontiers of knowledge on the risk of exceeding key climate TPs and their impact on ecological systems, biodiversity and society. The TP risk register will contribute to the European Climate Adaptation Platform; Climate-ADAPT, national adaptation strategies and exchange knowledge with the EU’s Missions on Adaptation to Climate Change, Climate Neutral and Smart Cities, and Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030, to help inform a climate resilient Europe by 2030. The World Bank estimates more than 100 million people will be dragged into poverty by 2030 due to climate change. Identification of Early Warning Indicators for tipping elements and potential cascades will support policy makers in assessing and responding to new risks, enable smarter adaptation for EU and international development goals. (SO6, SO7, SO8, SO9)

#EI1 Advancing knowledge and providing solutions in any of the following areas: Earth system science; Pathways to climate neutrality; Climate change adaptation; Climate services; Social science for climate action; and Better understanding of climate-ecosystems interactions.

TipESM will deliver new capabilities to assess the risk of exceeding key climate TPs, and associated ecological and societal impacts. The project uses the most recent ESMs, enabling investigation of how interactions and feedbacks across physical and biogeochemical systems influence the likelihood and impact of crossing different TPs. New techniques to deliberately induce climate TEs in ESMs will be developed. The TipESM team includes

social & ecological impact scientists, who will assess the role of climate change, changes in climate extremes and TEs on society and ecosystems. Impact models will be used to analyse multi-sectoral and regional impacts, including storm surges, tropical cyclones, species extinction and tropical diseases. TipESM will deliver unique information on the risk of reaching and exceeding TPs for various emission scenarios and temperature targets and guidance for safe mitigation pathways and adaptation strategies.

#EI2 Contributing substantially to key international assessments such as those of IPCC, IPBES or the European Environment Agency (e.g. SOER).

The high standing of TipESM consortium members will ensure our work influences international science bodies contributing to future UNFCCC, WMO, IPCC, FutureEarth, AMAP, IPBES, EEA and other assessments. TipESM partners have significant experience as IPCC AR authors and lead-authors. Results of TipESM will address key knowledge gaps and provide increased confidence in assessments of climate TEs and their impacts in the future Assessments. TipESM partners include former and recent steering and committee members of several WCRP Core projects and working groups, e.g., the WCRPJSC, NEMO-consortium, and a number of CMIP6 MIPs (e.g. ISMIP6, C4MIP, ScenarioMIP). Through these bodies, TipESM will help shape future priorities in Earth system modelling, scenario development, climate services, climate impact assessment and science-policy interaction. TipESM will contribute to the WCRP Lighthouse Activities, particularly to all five of the science themes in *Safe Landing Climates*, and to *Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change and Digital Earth*. TipESM will provide a strong European leadership in CMIP7 and to TIPMIP, ISIMIP (PIK leads), CORDEX (SMHI hosts the IPO) and the North Atlantic Hosing MIP (NAHosMIP) activities.

#EI3 Strengthening the European Research Area on climate change.

TipESM involves a multidisciplinary team of experts in ESMs, TP analysis, climate impacts and policy communication and engagement. Team members have leading roles in many international programs, bringing a wealth of experience and synergy with other national and European activities. The project will develop new capabilities to identify TP risks harnessing some of Europe’s most powerful supercomputing infrastructure. Through a coordinated European effort and collaboration with WCRP TIPMIP project and other ESM-centres around the world, TipESM will pave the way to an internationally coordinated ESM experiment protocol to support TP research worldwide. TipESM will play a leading role providing research evidence on TPs and their impacts to EU mitigation and adaptation policies through an experienced science to policy team who have worked extensively with EU policymakers. The project has a pivotal role training Early Career Researchers fostering future European talent.

#EI4 Increasing the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate change for use by policy makers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens.

TipESM will implement a range of Open Science practices (§1.2.6) to ensure stakeholders are engaged in the research process in the project (co-production and benefit from accessible research results. Outputs will be tailored to particular audiences, to ensure there is a beneficial and productive engagement that builds understanding, transparency and trust. With EU, international and national policy communities we will build on existing relationships and expand these as required. Public engagement will ensure an understanding of the risks of TPs, the need for immediate climate action and adaptation will be discussed actively. We will focus on Youth Action groups, schools and journalists, the latter to ensure widespread coverage of project results. TipESM will ensure that our results are robust, through coordination international CMIP7 and TIPMIP activities.

2.1.2 Scale and significance of the project’s contribution

Advancing knowledge and providing solutions - Research into climate TPs/abrupt changes is still an emerging area, but will be hugely significant going forwards in informing mitigation pathways and adaptation policies. There is a need to manage the socio-economic and environmental risks of TPs that might be triggered as the climate warms and an opportunity to influence international policy in areas such as disease management, health, biodiversity and conservation. In the TP research field, on average there have been around 4 publications per month over the last 2 years on Web of Science - so it will be easy to see the difference papers from TipESM will make in this field. Novel research will be published in open access journals only and promoted via social media. Papers will be complemented with presentations at major conferences (e.g. EGU, AGU) to ensure researchers across the world are informed of our experiments and results. Simulation data will be open access, enabling downscaling by regional models (e.g. CORDEX) and use by the wider impacts community (e.g. ISIMIP). Contribution to WCRP CMIP intercomparison

projects, TIPMIP and other activities will ensure a global reach. Collaboration with ISIMIP ensures connection with 17 impact sectors and around 220 impacts/protocol models. Users of ISIMIP products include scientists, international and regional policy and decision makers, funding agencies, and other. TipESM partners bring a wealth of connections with national, European and international projects which extend the reach of the project across a range of disciplines.

Contributing substantially to key international assessments - TipESM features many partners who are leading players in WCRP, CMIP and IPCC. The project will play a leading role in ESM simulation (e.g. TIPMIP) that will support upcoming assessments. These will have global reach in international policy arenas with a visible media and public outreach. We will bridge across IPCC WGI and WGII to address the need for risk management information for decision makers. A significant contribution will result from the TP risk register that will update results in the IPCC AR6-WGII report (Pörtner et al., 2022). Working with other projects, our science2policy events, briefings and COP side events will focus on engaging with key EU and national policymakers to ensure that TipESM results have maximum impact.

Strengthening the European Research Area on climate change - New capabilities will be shared with the international research community, across areas such as Earth system modelling and science, TP analysis, ecosystem, societal and biodiversity impacts. The project will contribute to EU adaptation and mitigation policies and underpin a climate resilient Europe. As the EU is a key negotiator in international climate policy, we envisage an important role for our project in this space. TipESM researchers and our engagement team will mentor Early Career Researchers in the project. With regard to gender equality, TipESM is in the strong position of having a female Project Coordinator and 7 women in leading project roles.

Improving the knowledge base on climate change for use by policy makers, practitioners, stakeholders and citizens - All partners come from a strong base of connecting with users, including climate services, policy and society. Specialists in communication, knowledge integration and public-engagement are integrated in the project. TipESM builds its policy engagement through existing connections with decision makers (including projects CRESCENDO, ESM2025, OptimESM), with the European Commission (DGs RTD, CLIMA, ENV, SANTE) and national governments. We will co-design and co-produce activities to ensure a common understanding and a take-up of results. Working with a focused policy group will ensure we meet the needs of stakeholders. The culmination of the project will be a TPs risk register and assessment of mitigation pathways and safe operating spaces for humanity and ecosystems. Providing an estimate of the remaining carbon budget to minimise the risk of crossing TPs will inform EU policies and ensure Europe is as climate resilient as possible.

2.1.3 Requirements and potential barriers in achieving the outcomes and impacts

HPC infrastructure: TipESM is reliant on continued investment by national and European research agencies to maintain world-leading HPC infrastructure and data centres, with well trained staff. Lack of funding or delays in HPC infrastructure access and investment could undermine or limit the ESM simulations to be carried out. Project partners have long standing relations with national and European HPC facilities and envisage continued and sufficient access to realise the project goals.

Changes in Climate Policy & Engagement: Significant changes in the direction of policies, potentially in response to risks/disasters/social pressure, might occur during the project. Regular engagement with policymakers from the start will keep TipESM up-to-date with developments. TipESM will cluster with other projects, where relevant, to share information and provide an efficient interface with policy to avoid stakeholder fatigue.

Occurrence/detection of a climate TE in the real world: It is not inconceivable that exceedance of a climate TP is detected in the real world during the project lifetime. Such an occurrence would likely require a rapid change in emphasis for the project and potentially a demand for new and urgent science support for decision-making.

Difficulty simulating/sampling TEs in coupled ESMs. While there are examples of plausible TPs simulated in ESMs (e.g. Parry et al. 2022), there is also a suggestion that ESMs may be overly stable with respect to certain tipping elements (e.g. AMOC stability, Liu et al. 2017). Furthermore, many “at risk of tipping” phenomena are in relatively new components of our ESMs (e.g. interactive Antarctic ice sheets, Amazon forests, permafrost thaw) so there is only limited knowledge about how well these components represent the processes that underpin the likelihood of tipping. While we envisage that TEs will be detected in our warming overshoot and stabilisation runs (*TipESM_core*), we include a set of experiments where we will force TEs to occur in the models (*TipESM_forced*).

Difficulty hiring suitably trained researchers. While TipESM partners are experienced in recruiting and training new researchers, the pool of young researchers, with suitable training, is not large and the salaries offered in scientific research are not always competitive. This creates a risk that we fail to recruit sufficient and/or suitable researchers to carry out the ambitious plans of the project. We will work hard to avoid this outcome and use our extensive international networks to attract the best young talent we can into the project.

2.2 Measures to maximise impact - Dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC)

DEC (WPs9-10) will play a key role maximising the scientific, environmental and societal impact of the project. All partners will contribute to these activities, whose purpose is to enhance European leadership in climate science, promote uptake of informed climate adaptation, increase awareness of the need for a societal transition to a climate neutral and resilient society, and ensure the legacy of the project.

DEC will be led by DMI, supported by SMHI and UNIVLEEDS. The three organisations have a strong track record in communication, policy engagement and climate services and have led H2020/HORIZON projects before, with a successful track record of dissemination and communication. The TipESM consortium also includes experienced dissemination practitioners (e.g. ISGlobal, PIK, IPSL, the Met Office). The strategy and activities to maximise project impact will be outlined in the **Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (DECP)** at the start of the project and implemented through tasks in WP9-10. This plan will detail communication objectives, strategies and channels, definition of target audiences (see Tables 2.2a & 2.3 for a preliminary list), an editorial calendar for communication and dissemination of project outcomes and to map out relevant events such as conferences and workshops for promoting project results. All activities will be monitored through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), followed up and updated to maximise their impact. This plan will be updated several times during the project, and a final evaluation of the impact of our DEC will be made at the end of the project (M46, D10.3).

2.2.1 Dissemination

The dissemination strategy will tailor communication of project results to specific audiences. We identify three primary audiences: the scientific community, policymakers and the general public. The **scientific community** includes climate change, Earth system and impact modelling researchers, social scientists, climate services and climate adaptation communities and teams developing future emission and mitigation pathways. Peer-reviewed publications and scientific conferences will be a major dissemination activity for this audience. Science-to-policy events will target **policymakers** at multiple levels of governance (municipal, regional, national, European) to support EU Adaptation and Mitigation Strategies and to maximise the impact at a regional level of the Mission on adaptation to climate change. Policy briefs (WP9-10) will be complemented with ad hoc dissemination and policy engagement activities (e.g., ECCA/COP side events, virtual policy roundtables) to convey the role climate services can play in informing and supporting policies and initiatives, such as the Partnership on Climate Adaptation and the Climate Pact. **The general public, including schools and universities** will be targeted mainly through social media and involvement in science fairs, roadshows and national/European science outreach events.

An initial outline of activities is provided in Table 2.2a. A visual project identity will be developed to create cohesion across project communications, ensuring materials and project outputs will be easily identifiable.

Table 2.2a: Maximising impact: Dissemination and Communication activities, their expected impact, audience, time of occurrence and KPIs.

D&C measures	Expected Impact	Target audience(s)	Time: KPIs
Project website	A central reference point with a cohesive visual identity and user- friendly information, highlighting project results through a variety of media.	General public, Research & Academic community, stakeholders, policymakers	M2: > 200 visits per month
Newsletters Flyers, Factsheets, Infographics, leaflets	Dissemination of research findings tailored to each audience, using accessible language and visuals. Highlighting potential impacts on society, ecosystems and biodiversity.	Local, national & EU stakeholders; Policymakers; Science & Scicomm communities; Journalists; Horizon Magazine & Results Platform	Monthly via LinkedIn (+4000 followers)
Policy briefings, COP side events, town halls, EU Science2Policy events	Targeted at policymakers (EC, EU Parliament) to ensure project outputs can be easily understood and integrated. Arranged in collaboration with OptimESM and ESM2025.	Policymakers, Government, EU agencies, adaptation science community	M30 & M45: Policy briefs, events; > 500 attendees

Roadshow	A series of events (online, in-person) and communications generating buzz around project results; timed with larger conferences, events and public science festivals to ensure maximum visibility.	General public, user communities, Research & Academic Community; local, regional, national & EU stakeholders.	One roadshow with small events
Social Media (Twitter/Mastodon/LinkedIn/YouTube campaigns and presence)	Connecting stakeholders with the project from the start and to research outcomes. Targeted campaigns at various intervals to reach specific audiences.	Research & Academic community; Stakeholders at local, regional, national & EU levels, media, general public	Continually: > 2000 Followers
Press releases and media communication	Reaching & informing a larger audience through targeted press communications e.g. CarbonBrief, Horizon Magazine	Research & Academic community, Policy makers, governments, general public	5-8 press releases: 100s of readers
Short videos and webinars	Short videos to support dissemination activities, explain concepts and increase awareness of the project.	Society at large, including schools and universities.	Continually: > 3000 viewers
Open Science tools	Tools to ensure exploitation of data beyond the project for use in special reports, etc.	Research & Academic community; local, regional, national & EU stakeholders	M45 (project legacy): > 200 visits per month
Open-access journals, scientific conferences, workshops/webinars	Publication and discussion of research outcomes to ensure a broad advancement in TP research and its impacts and continued research beyond the project.	Research & Academic community (ESM modellers, TP and climate impact researchers)	Continually: > 50 articles > 30 conference presentations

2.2.2 Exploitation

The TipESM exploitation strategy aims to make use of the project results for scientific, policy and societal purposes. TipESM considers four categories of exploitable results, see table 2.2b: Scientific knowledge, knowledge for policy and society, methods/protocols, and data, tools and applications. The exploitation plan and guidelines for long-term exploitation of results beyond the project lifetime will be developed in WP9-10. Exploitation activities will be supervised by the project coordinator in collaboration with all partners and alongside data and knowledge protection and management. Activities will be linked to the Open Science commitments and procedures under the FAIR principles (§1.2.6). All exploitation activities will be closely linked to planned dissemination and communication activities to boost exploitation potential beyond the project end. Key pathways to exploitation will be included in the initial draft of the exploitation plan. This will evolve during the project, with the plan updated halfway through the project, with a report on exploitation activities, and consolidated at the end to draw-up final exploitation plans for the project legacy.

KER will link closely to our Open Science commitments and Data Management (§1.2.6 and §1.2.7).

Table 2.2b: Some of the key exploitable results (KER) expected in the project. *See §1.1.3 for additional information.

§2.2.3 Communication

Type of KER	Key Exploitable Results
Data, tools and applications	Ensemble of ESM simulations to explore TPs. Output from TipESM made available on the ESGF. TP risk register. Interactive mapping system with geographical impacts of climate TPs on ecosystem and society. A Register of Early Warning Indicators for climate and ecological TPs, including guidance for future observation networks. Updated catalogue TPs and tipping cascades in the Earth system. Datasets on hazard exposure for tipping in social systems.

Knowledge for policy and society	Policy briefs and insights summarizing latest knowledge on TPs and their impacts. A report on climate thresholds that lead to tipping in ecological and social systems; Lessons learned in ESM modelling. Transdisciplinary approaches in EU projects. Synthesis of tipping elements and thresholds across terrestrial and marine ecosystems. Policy workshops on the risk and potential consequences of crossing climate TPs. Online tutorial explaining TPs to e.g. school students (16-18 year old) linked to their curriculum.
Methods/protocols	Protocol for coupled ESM simulations for TIPMIP and realisation of these experiments with the project ESMs. Techniques for triggering climate TPs in ESMs (e.g. so-called “What-If” scenarios). Integration of climate impact models with observations to identify tipping in ecological and social systems. Improved integration of Earth system and climate impact modelling.
Scientific knowledge	Scientific publications and deliverables of interest for exploitation by other scientists or experts from the diverse disciplines contributing to the project.

2.2.3 Communication

Project communication includes both internal and external communication. Internal communication will be coordinated by WP9-10 to ensure a clear and effective communication between partners. The purpose of external communication is twofold: increase the project visibility to support clustering and synergies at European and international level and contribute to broad public engagement activities.

Regarding synergies with other initiatives (see §1.2.2), WP9-10 will provide coordination support for clustering activities at European level and give visibility to international cooperation with initiatives beyond Europe (e.g., WCRP, WMO, FutureEarth). Public engagement will reach out to society through broad actions, with a focus on youth action groups, schools, civil society, and journalists specialising in climate and the environment. We will develop communication products and campaigns designed for easy sharing on social media, which is an important and low-cost mode of public engagement. Such activities will provide appropriate materials and messages to increase awareness of why adaptation strategies are necessary to prepare for future extreme weather and climate. There is a general lack of young women scientists in high-profile or leading roles, despite making up an increasing percentage of the STEM student body. To address this, TipESM will encourage researchers in the project to engage in initiatives like Pint of Science, European Researchers’ Night and the International Day of Women and Girls in Science. Female, non-binary and male scientists will contribute to these activities to raise awareness on how science supports climate change adaptation and mitigation. We will particularly encourage participation of TipESM female scientists as role models for young girls.

Table 2.3 Summary of the project impact - pathway towards impact canvas					
SPECIFIC NEEDS	EXPECTED RESULTS	D&E&C MEASURES	TARGET GROUPS	OUTCOMES	IMPACTS
To deliver new capability to assess the risk of exceeding key climate TPs and their impact on ecosystems and society	<p>ESM experiment protocol for simulating climate TPs (TIPMIP) (Deliverables D1.1, D1.3)</p> <p>Techniques to deliberately induce TEs in coupled ESMs documented (D1.2)</p> <p>Catalogue of TPs, analysis of feedback chains & downstream effects (D2.1, 2.2, 2.3)</p> <p>Analysis of the robustness and (ir)reversibility of identified TPs and their drivers, including climate thresholds for ecological and societal TPs (D3.1, D3.2)</p> <p>A register of Early Warning Indicators (EWI) for TPs in the Earth system (D4.1, D4.2)</p> <p>Analysis of the risk for TP cascades in the Earth system and the role of extreme events (D5.1, D5.2)</p>	<p>Dissemination: Scientific advances through peer-reviewed articles, conference proceedings, press releases, and popular science articles.</p> <p>Exploitation: Models, documentation, protocols, code and data documented and curated for use by scientists outside the project (FAIR); Part of project exploitation plan.</p> <p>Communication: Showcase results on project website, at events and on social media; animated video explainers for the public; Local-level communication campaign and Roadshow for policymakers; Clustering with other EU projects clusters and Horizon Europe missions).</p>	<p>Earth system modellers and scientists, climate, physics, biogeochemistry, biology, social sciences, health research communities,</p> <p>CMIP, major assessments IPCC, ESA, WCRP</p> <p>TIPMIP, EEA, IPBES</p> <p>Copernicus & Climate Adapt services</p> <p>Researchers of: TPs, abrupt ecosystem change, and potential mitigation and adaptation strategies.</p> <p>Public citizens - especially youth action groups, schools and journalists</p>	<p>#EO1 New or improved models for climate predictions or projections, which take into account climate-related TPs and their impacts, and are relevant for major assessments like those of the IPCC and IPBES</p> <p>#EO2 Better understanding of potential compound or cascading effects on climate, ecosystems and society as a consequence of crossing specific TPs.</p> <p>#EO3 Increased capacity to identify unknown tipping elements and early warning signals when a TP is approached.</p>	<p>#EI1 Advancing knowledge and solutions in the following areas: Earth system science; Pathways to climate neutrality; Climate change adaptation; Climate services; Social science for climate action; and understanding of climate-ecosystems interactions.</p> <p>#EI2 Contribute substantially to key international assessments; IPCC, IPBES, EEA (SOER).</p> <p>#EI3 Strengthening the European Research Area on climate change.</p>

<p>Guidance for policy and decision-making on mitigation pathways, safe operating spaces for humanity and ecosystems and adaptation strategies</p>	<p>Synthesis of tipping elements and thresholds across the terrestrial, marine and cryosphere systems. Datasets on hazard exposure for tipping in social systems (D6.1, 6.2, 6.3)</p> <p>Quantification of the societal and ecosystem impacts of crossing climate TPs (D7.1-D7.3)</p> <p>Development of risk register and assessment of mitigation pathways and safe operating spaces for humanity and ecosystems (D8.1-D8.3)</p> <p>Policy briefings and clustering events on TPs, risks, early warning indicators, societal and ecosystem impacts and safe future mitigation pathways (D9.5, D9.7, D10.1, D10.2)</p>	<p>Dissemination: ECCA (and other) conference sessions/presentations, COP side events, scientific papers, popular science articles, Horizon Results platform.</p> <p>Exploitation: Exploitation plan; Linking to other platforms (e.g., ClimateAdapt)</p> <p>Communication: Integrate the benefits of planning for extreme weather and climate events into materials for local policy and decision makers; Animated video explainers; Clustering activities</p>	<p>Researchers using output from ESMs (e.g. climate impacts community)</p> <p>Major assessments; IPCC, IPBES, EEA, WCRP, WMO</p> <p>Decision making and policy making (international, EU, national), ESA (for future missions), Future Earth</p> <p>Adaptation strategists, NGOs, agriculture, fisheries, health, natural disasters. Including European Climate and Health Observatory, European Centre for Disease Prevention & Control, UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, UNEP</p> <p>Activities under Horizon Europe Clusters: CL5 (Climate, Energy, Mobility), CL4 (Digital, Industry, Space) and CL6 (Food, Natural Resources, Agriculture, Environment)</p> <p>Horizon Europe Missions including “Adaptation to Climate Change”, “Climate Neutral and Smart Cities” and “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”</p>	<p>#E02 Better understanding of potential compound or cascading effects on climate, ecosystems and society from crossing specific TPs.</p> <p>#E03 Increased capacity to identify unknown tipping elements and early warning signals when a TP is approached.</p> <p>#E04 Contribution to mitigation policies with regard to the Paris Agreement and the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, taking into account the precautionary principle, with respect to abrupt responses, hysteresis and other non-linear behaviour of the Earth system.</p> <p>#E05 Input to adaptation strategies for the most affected regions, globally, addressing the risks of crossing climatic TPs and related impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity.</p>	<p>All expected impacts #E11, #E12, E13, and #E14 Increasing the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate and Earth system change for use by policy makers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens.</p>
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